

HyCARE

Hydrogen CARRIER for Renewable Energy Storage

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Executive summary

The deliverable D8.2 has the purpose of evaluating the **techno-economic feasibility** of the *HyCARE* system, as an alternative hydrogen storage solution to well established technologies.

For this reason, the report is divided into several parts with the aim to compare, from a technical and economic point of view, this technology to the other storage solutions available on the market. The analysis focuses on two different case studies, a **base case** and a **normalized one**. A **sensitivity analysis** on the main critical factors is also performed for each scenario, to estimate the impact of some key parameters on the costs of each examined technology.

The deliverable also investigates the upscaling of the various storage technologies, to understand which technology scales better when storage volumes grow and to understand which technology is most suitable for a given storage size.

The electric energy storage comparison between Battery Energy Storage System (BESS) and *HyCARE* system was not carried out because, as explained in the report, the two systems are not comparable cause the boundary conditions and the components involved are different.

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Glossary

%_{wt}	Weight percentage
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
B.S.	Base Scenario
BoP	Balance of Plant
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
capex	Specific Capital Expenditure
CEPCI	Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index
COP	Coefficient of Performance
DBT	Dibenzyltoluene
EER	Energy Efficiency Ratio
GH₂	Gaseous Hydrogen
HHV	Higher Heating Value
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
kW_{th}	Thermal Kilowatt
LCoS	Levelized Cost of Storage
LH₂	Liquid Hydrogen
LHV	Lower Heating Value
LOHCs	Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers
MACRS	Modified Accelerated Cost Recovery System
MCH	Methylcyclohexane
ND	Not Determined
N.S.	Normalised Scenario
O&M	Operational and Maintenance
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
opex	Specific Operational Expenditure
PCM	Phase Change Material
TCO	Total Cost of Ownership

1. Introduction and purpose

The *HyCARE* project aims to develop a solid-state hydrogen storage system in large scale, as an alternative to the most classical hydrogen storage technologies, such as compressed gaseous form and liquid form. Different storage options have different characteristics, not only in terms of cost but also in relation to systems capacities and performances. Figure 1-1 displays the gravimetric and volumetric capacities of some hydrogen storage technologies: options such as liquid hydrogen (LH₂), liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs) and some hydrides allow to obtain high gravimetric capacities, compared to gaseous form (GH₂). However, their capital and operational expenditures are high due to the liquefaction/hydrogenation and release/dehydrogenation processes required.

FIGURE 1-1: COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT HYDROGEN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES.¹

Another aspect to consider is that different boundary conditions heavily influence the cost-effectiveness of each storage technology. As an example, the liquefaction process is highly expensive, both in terms of capital expenditure (CAPEX) and operational expenditure (OPEX). This causes the liquid form to be a cost-effective solution, compared to gaseous hydrogen, only for large sizes, where the large amount of hydrogen produced causes a reduction of its specific cost.

The purpose of this deliverable is to analyze some performance indicators (KPIs), both of technical and economical nature, to assess which storage form results to be the most cost-effective for different storage sizes. Two different analyses will be provided:

- **Single size:** *HyCARE* system capacity (40 kg of stored hydrogen) will be used as nominal capacity to compare different storage options.
- **Multiple size:** a scale-up of the 40-kg model will be provided, to evaluate how all technologies perform at different scales (small to medium and medium to large).

The technologies which will be compared, involving both solid, liquid, and gaseous H₂ phase, are:

- Gaseous hydrogen – compressed at 30 bar.
- Gaseous hydrogen – compressed at 350 bar.
- Liquid hydrogen.

¹ Reuß, Markus & Grube, Thomas & Robinius, Martin & Preuster, Patrick & Wasserscheid, Peter & Stolten, Detlef. (2017). Seasonal storage and alternative carriers: A flexible hydrogen supply chain model. *Applied Energy*. 200. 290–302. 10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.05.050.

- Liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC).
- Metal hydride.
- *HyCARE* system.

2. Methodology

In this section, the approach that has been followed to evaluate the KPIs of the hydrogen storage technologies considered, will be detailed, and explained. First, the main KPIs have been identified to properly characterize different storage options, from a techno-economic point of view. The parameters that have been considered are technology neutral and possess a cross-over nature so to have feasible applicability in all the systems that are studied in this work. In this regard, these parameters are listed and described in Table 2-1 (technical KPIs) and in Table 2-2 (economic KPIs).

TABLE 2-1: TECHNICAL KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS LIST.

Parameter	Unit	Description
Storage efficiency	kWh/kg	Amount of energy needed to store 1 kg of H ₂ amount of energy needed to store 1 kg of H ₂ .
Gravimetric energy density	kg-H ₂ /kg-system	Gravimetric capacity of the storage system expressed in kg of stored H ₂ per kg of the vessel system (plus eventual carrier).
Volumetric energy density	kg-H ₂ /m ³	Volumetric capacity of the storage system is expressed in kg of stored H ₂ per unit volume of the vessel system.
Lifetime	yrs	Storage system lifetime, considered as the minimum between vessel's lifetime and carrier's one.

TABLE 2-2: ECONOMIC KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS LIST.

Parameter	Unit	Description
CAPEX	€	Cost of the hydrogen storage system includes direct capital costs and indirect capital costs.
OPEX	€/yr	Annual operational and maintenance (O&M) cost, including running costs (electricity, heat, and cooling water), labor, maintenance, and repairs.
TCO	€	Total cost of ownership (CAPEX plus OPEX over the entire lifetime).
LCoS	€/kg-H ₂	Levelized cost of storage, evaluated considering the ratio between the total cost of ownership (TCO) and the potential storage of hydrogen during the lifetime.

Regarding technical KPIs, the abovementioned parameters have been evaluated by looking at updated, literature references or datasheets of commercial products. For the *HyCARE* system, reported results are directly given by project partners or evaluated from their information. As to economic KPIs, an analytical model has been implemented to estimate all the desired indicators, and model description and hypothesis are provided in Chapter 0.

2.1 Scenarios definition

For all different technologies, the control volume of the system must have the same inlet and outlet conditions, to ensure a proper and consistent evaluation. In this study, two different use case scenarios are used to define these border conditions:

- **Base Scenario:** based on the production and consumption profiles used within *HyCARE* D6.3 analysis.
- **Normalised Scenario:** in which the production profile of the “Base Scenario” is scaled to reach a cumulative daily production equal to the cumulative daily consumption.

Figure 2-1 shows the hydrogen production and consumption profiles used in the “Base Scenario”, while Figure 2-2 shows the ones used in the “Normalised Scenario”. Both profiles are daily based, and they will be kept constant for all the working days, for simplicity’s sake. In this way, no seasonal change in hydrogen production and consumption will be considered.

FIGURE 2-1: “BASE SCENARIO” HYDROGEN PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION DAILY PROFILES.

FIGURE 2-2: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” HYDROGEN PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION DAILY PROFILES.

While in the “*Base Scenario*” the filling and emptying processes are separated (i.e., first the storage system is filled completely and then it’s emptied completely), in the “*Normalised Scenario*” both steps occur simultaneously. In this way, if the produced hydrogen overcomes the consumed one, the excess one is sent to the storage system; on the contrary, if the consumed hydrogen is more than the produced one, the difference is drawn from the storage system. The instant stored hydrogen trend, on daily base for Normalised scenario, is reported in Figure 2-3. The assumption of a 0 kg-initial load is not realistic, because the amount of hydrogen stored will go below 0 kg during the first half of the day, and it’s been assumed only to show the daily trend.

FIGURE 2-3: DAILY STORED HYDROGEN PROFILE IN THE “NORMALISED SCENARIO”²

Therefore, for the “*Normalised Scenario*” not all the produced hydrogen will be stored, but only the excess production. Figure 2-4 shows the net input and output profiles for the storage system in the “*Normalised Scenario*” (i.e., the production profile minus the bypass hydrogen and the consumption profile minus the bypass hydrogen, respectively).

² The corresponding daily accumulation figure for the base scenario is not reported, since despite being a daily profile, as the production and consumption flowrate are different, the total loading and unloading of the storage system will take place over several days, however at a conceptual level, the stored hydrogen profile should have the characteristic sawtooth shape.

FIGURE 2-4: INPUT AND OUTPUT HYDROGEN PROFILES FOR THE “NORMALISED SCENARIO” STORAGE SYSTEM.

The analysis of two different scenarios is carried out because some technological sizes (e.g., compressors, liquefiers, evaporators, hydrogenation, and dehydrogenation units) depend on the flow that the technology can process. Hence, different flow rates impact the economic analysis and its results. For these components, the equipment sizing will be carried out considering the maximum inlet or outlet hydrogen flow (peak values). Figure 2-5 shows a framework of the single size control volume inlet and outlet conditions, while Table 2-3 summarizes the working regime assumptions made, for both scenarios and for all the storage technologies, within the single size analysis. All systems are fueled with gaseous hydrogen at 30 bar and release gaseous hydrogen at 2 bar.

FIGURE 2-5: CONTROL VOLUME USED FOR EACH TECHNOLOGY IN THE SINGLE SIZE ANALYSIS.

TABLE 2-3: WORKING REGIME ASSUMPTIONS – SINGLE SIZE 40 KG OF HYDROGEN.

Parameter	“Base Scenario”	“Normalised Scenario”	Description
Annual operating hours	8760 h	8760 h	Total annual operating hours, comprehensive accumulation, storage, and release processes.
Plant lifetime	30 yr	30 yr	Lifetime used for the comparison of all storage systems.
Storage dead time	0 h	-	Time gap between the end of the accumulation phase and the beginning of the release phase.
Daily H ₂ production	29.1 Nm ³	123.7 Nm ³	Hydrogen daily cumulative production.
Daily H ₂ consumption	123.7 Nm ³	123.7 Nm ³	Hydrogen daily cumulative consumption.
Total filling time	370.0 h	-	Time required to fill the 40-kgH ₂ storage system.
Total emptying time	87.0 h	-	Time required to empty the 40-kgH ₂ storage system.
Maximum filling flow	10 Nm ³ /h	42.5 Nm ³ /h	Maximum flow registered during the daily production profile.
Maximum emptying flow	10 Nm ³ /h	10 Nm ³ /h	Maximum flow registered during the daily consumption profile.

Regarding the multiple-size analysis of both the scenarios put forward, it will be considered not only a scale-up of the storage system, but also a scale-up of the hydrogen production and consumption processes. This is obtained by defining the ratio R between capacity and maximum flow (Eq. 2.1) and by keeping it constant during the scale-up process.

$$R[h] = \frac{Capacity[kg]}{Maximum\ Flow[kg/h]} \quad (2.1)$$

In this way, systems storage capacity and maximum flows (filling and emptying) will vary, while the filling and emptying time will remain constant instead. Of course, R will vary according to the scenario and the stream (inlet or outlet) chosen. A framework of the border conditions, for the multiple-size analysis, is proposed in Figure 2-6.

FIGURE 2-6 CONTROL VOLUME USED IN THE MULTIPLE-SIZE ANALYSIS FOR:
(A) THE “BASE SCENARIO” AND (B) THE “NORMALISED SCENARIO”.

2.2 Hydrogen storage

In this section, the storage options previously mentioned will be briefly described and explored, in order to find the subcomponents needed for each technology, to meet the border conditions set in Figure 2-5 and Figure 2-6. Moreover, each subcomponent will be preliminary designed to calculate its capital and operational expenditures.

2.2.1 Gaseous hydrogen – 30 bar

Storage in pressure vessels is the most common technological solution for storing hydrogen. Due to its low volumetric density at atmospheric pressure, hydrogen needs to be compressed at high pressure to reduce the vessel size and to reach appreciable energy densities. The compressed gaseous form represents the simplest storage option because the only equipment needed is a compressor, a pressure vessel, and Balance of Plant (BoP) components³. These latter are valves, sensors, and regulators (flowrate, temperature, and pressure), safety devices (rupture disk, pressure relief device) and tubing. A schematic of a compressed hydrogen storage system, for mobility applications, is described in Figure 2-7.

³ A. Amos, “Costs of Storing and Transporting Hydrogen” NREL/TP-570-25106, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, November 1998.

FIGURE 2-7: COMPRESSED HYDROGEN STORAGE SYSTEM SCHEMATIC⁴.

¹ Schematic based on the requirements defined in the draft European regulation "Hydrogen Vehicles: On-Board Storage Systems" and US Patent 6,041,762.
² Secondary Pressure Regulator located in Fuel Control Module of the Fuel Cell System.

If the pressure drop between the source of hydrogen and the tank can be neglected, no compressor is needed because the inlet pressure equals the storage one. In this way, the 30 bar compressed hydrogen system consists in merely the vessel, as pointed out in GH2-30 bar control volume, represented in Figure 2-8.

FIGURE 2-8: CONTROL VOLUME FOR THE GH2-30BAR SYSTEM.

⁴ K. Law, J. Rosenfeld, V. Han, M. Chan, H. Chiang, J. Leonard, "Energy Hydrogen Storage Cost Analysis", TIAX LLC, 11.03.2013.

2.2.2 Gaseous hydrogen – 350 bar

In case of storage pressures larger than 30 bar, a compression system is required. A schematic of the whole storage technology is given in Figure 2-9. A preliminary system design is necessary to understand how many compression stages are required to deliver hydrogen with the proper outlet conditions. Based on the requirements of *American Petroleum Institute Standard 618, Reciprocating Compressors for Petroleum, Chemical, and Gas Service*, the maximum allowable gas temperature is taken to be 275 °F (135 °C)⁵.

FIGURE 2-9: CONTROL VOLUME FOR THE GH2-350BAR SYSTEM.

The isentropic outlet temperature T_{out} , for each stage, can be obtained through Eq. 2.2, where T_{in} is the inlet temperature, γ the diatomic constant factor, P_{in} and P_{out} the inlet and outlet pressure, respectively⁵.

$$T_{out} = T_{in} \cdot \left(\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{\gamma}} \quad (2.2)$$

If all the stage compressors have the same isentropic efficiency, the optimal compression ratio β is expressed by Eq. 2.3, in which n represents the overall number of stages⁶.

$$\beta = \left(\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (2.3)$$

Therefore, assuming a certain number of stages and combining Eq. 2.2 and 2.3, it's possible to compute the outlet temperature for each stage and establish if it exceeds the assumed limit temperature of 135 °C. Hypothesizing $n = 2$, the outlet temperature exceeds the imposed limit, hence $n = 3$ is chosen. To cool the discharged gas, a heat exchanger is placed after each compression stage:

⁵ Nexant, H2A hydrogen delivery infrastructure analysis models and conventional pathway options analysis results, 2008.

⁶ López-Paniagua I, Rodríguez-Martín J, Sánchez-Orgaz S, Roncal-Casano JJ. Step by Step Derivation of the Optimum Multistage Compression Ratio and an Application Case. *Entropy*. 2020; 22(6):678. <https://doi.org/10.3390/e22060678>.

these heat exchangers cool the outlet hydrogen down to 100 F (37.8°C), based on the system designed in the *H2A* analysis⁵. The cooling water is assumed to be produced through a refrigeration unit with an *energy efficiency ratio* (EER) of 2.5. The compressor isentropic efficiency is set equal to 0.88.

2.2.3 Liquid hydrogen

Apart from compressing gaseous hydrogen, liquid hydrogen is another viable solution for energy storage with appreciable energy densities. The liquid state results in significantly beneficial from a technical point of view in several applications. In the case of hydrogen, for transportation over long distances and for significant production volumes, liquid hydrogen might be addressed as a much better solution than compressed gas. Nevertheless, the fact that hydrogen liquefies at cryogenic temperature severely complex the storage conditions. In order to make it liquid, hydrogen requires high energetic consumption for cooling and additional components for gasifying it again at the outlet of the tank for final use. Figure 2-10 shows a possible process flow chart for a hydrogen liquefaction unit.

FIGURE 2-10: JOULE-THOMSON PROCESS WITH LIQUID NITROGEN PRECOOLING FOR HYDROGEN LIQUEFACTION.

In this framework, the storage vessel needs to strictly satisfy several requirements, ranging from high insulating material properties for avoiding heat losses to low surface-to-volume ratios for reducing heat exchange. In such sense, tanks generally have a spherical shape and need to be equipped with additional components such as safety devices, valves, and measurement tools. A major limitation in storing liquid hydrogen regards the boil-off losses. These are resulting from unavoidable heat coming into the vessel which increases hydrogen temperature and hence pressure. To maintain appropriate storage conditions, a portion of the stored hydrogen needs to be evacuated to the atmosphere.

Considering the boundary conditions shown in Figure 2-5, the overall system must be composed of a liquefaction section, an LH2 storage vessel and a vaporization section. A framework of the system is given in Figure 2-11. The liquid hydrogen is assumed to be stored at 2 bar and a temperature of -250 °C.

FIGURE 2-11: CONTROL VOLUME FOR THE LH2 SYSTEM.

2.2.4 Liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHC)

Energy carrier compounds can be defined as those substances which possess the ability of storing and releasing energy through specific chemical and physical processes. In this landscape, hydrogen can be considered as the form of stored energy through hydrogenation and dehydrogenation of liquid organic chemical species, which are indeed called liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs). The storage concept underlying LOHCs relies on the possibility of charging them with the desired hydrogen load, storing and transporting it for the final need, where the compound would be dehydrogenated. The hydrogen storage process requires a catalytic reaction with specific temperature and pressure conditions which are strictly related to the compound used as LOHC and to the catalyst that is responsible for driving the reaction^{1,7}. Numerous different chemicals have been studied as LOHCs in the last decades for increasing the efficiencies of this reversible hydrogenation/dehydrogenation cycle. Heterocyclic aromatic hydrocarbons such as *N*-ethylcarbazole have been first investigated, then research focused on aromatic hydrocarbons such as toluene/methylcyclohexane. Figure 2-12 gives an overview of the whole LOHC system, using dibenzyltoluene (DBT) as hydrogen carrier.

⁷ Aakko-Saksa, Päivi T., et al. "Liquid organic hydrogen carriers for transportation and storing of renewable energy—Review and discussion." *Journal of Power Sources* 396 (2018): 803-823

FIGURE 2-12: OVERVIEW OF THE LOHC SYSTEM⁸.

The overall LOHC system must be composed of a hydrogenation section, two LOHC storage vessels and a dehydrogenation section. A framework of the system is given in Figure 2-13. DBT will be chosen as liquid organic hydrogen carrier, considering a density of 921 kg/m³ and a gravimetric capacity of 6.2%_{wt}⁹. The cooling demand required for the hydrogenation step is assumed to be produced through a refrigeration unit with an *energy efficiency ratio* of 2.5, while the heat demand required for the dehydrogenation step is provided by a heat pump with a *coefficient of performance* (COP) of 3.

⁸ Martin Eypasch, Michael Schimpe, Aastha Kanwar, Tobias Hartmann, Simon Herzog, Torsten Frank, Thomas Hamacher, Model-based techno-economic evaluation of an electricity storage system based on Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers, Applied Energy, Volume 185, Part 1, 2017, Pages 320-330, ISSN 0306-2619, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.10.068>.

⁹ Hydrogen Supply and Transportation using Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (HySTOC), WP8 Business Development and sustainability – Concept Studies, Economic Analysis, Life Cycle Assessment D8.3 A preliminary feasibility study. 2019-06-30.

FIGURE 2-13: CONTROL VOLUME FOR THE LOHC SYSTEM.

2.2.5 Metal hydrides

Metal hydrides work as hydrogen storage technologies through the chemical bonding of hydrogen within the lattice structure of the materials. There is a wide operating range of temperatures and pressures for hydrides depending on the alloy chosen. Each alloy has different performance characteristics, such as cycle life and heat of reaction^{3,10,11,12}. Figure 2-14 shows the relationship between temperature and pressure during charge and discharge phases of the metal hydride. By increasing hydrogen partial pressure, the hydrogen diffuses in the metal or alloy, then it begins to bond to the metal. During the bonding period the pressure remains almost constant until a high percentage of the maximum storage capacity is reached: after that, higher pressures are required to reach the totality of the hydride storage capacity.

¹⁰ M. Dornheim, L. Baetcke, E. Akiba, J-R. Ares, T. Autrey, J. Barale, M. Baricco, K. Brooks, N. Chalkiadakis, V. Charbonnier. Research and development of hydrogen carrier based solutions for hydrogen compression and storage. *Progress in Energy*, Volume 4, Number 4. 2022. DOI 10.1088/2516-1083/ac7cb7

¹¹ L. Pasquini, K. Sakaki, E. Akiba, M. D Allendorf, E. Alvares, J-R. Ares, D. Babai, M. Baricoo, J. Bellosta von Colbe, M. Berezniysky. Magnesium- and intermetallic alloys-based hydrides for energy storage: modelling, synthesis and properties. *Progress in Energy*, Volume 4, Number 3. 2022. DOI 10.1088/2516-1083/ac7190

¹² M. Hirscher, V. A. Yartys, M. Baricco, J. Bellosta von Colbe, D. Blanchard, R. C. Bowman Jr., D. P. Broom, C. E. Buckley, F. Chang, P.Chen, Y. W.Cho, J-C Crivello, F. Cuevas, W. I.F. David, P. E. de Jongh, R. V. Denys, M. Dornheim, M. Felderhoff, Y. Filinchuk, G. E. Froudakis, C. Zlotea. Materials for hydrogen-based energy storage – past, recent progress and future outlook. *Journal of Alloys and Compounds*. 2020. doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.153548

FIGURE 2-14: METAL HYDRIDE PRESSURE BEHAVIOR¹³.

Storage vessels for these metal alloys require significant energy supply to release hydrogen, due to the strength of the chemical bonding involved in hydrogen absorption/desorption. The vessel which contains the hydride must be pressurized and be designed with a sufficient heat exchange area to allow rapid heat transfer for charging and discharging the hydride¹³. Moreover, it must be considered that the metal alloy needs to be activated to be ready for hydrogen charge/discharge processes. The activation is obtained through a certain number of absorption/desorption cycles, involving both a waste of hydrogen and a waste of heating/cooling energy.

Considering these aspects, the overall solid state storage system is composed of a storage tank, in which metal hydride pellets are placed, supplemented with a heat exchange section. A framework of the system is given in Figure 2-15. For this kind of storage, a TiFe-based compound is chosen as metal alloy. The cooling demand required for the absorption is assumed to be produced through a refrigeration unit (EER = 2.5), while the heat demand required for the desorption is provided by a heat pump (COP = 3).

¹³ S. Banerjee, P. Ruz. Synthesis and characterization of metal hydrides and their application. Handboon on synthesis strategies for advanced materials. 2021.

FIGURE 2-15: CONTROL VOLUME FOR THE METAL HYDRIDE SYSTEM.

2.2.6 HyCARE

The *HyCARE* system is an innovative hydrogen solid-state storage system based on metal hydrides. It differs from the metal hydride system because it's characterized by a new concept to minimize the expenses and improve the overall efficiency. More specifically, a phase change material (PCM) tank is placed next to each metal hydride vessel, to store and reuse part of the cooling/heating energy required for the absorption/desorption cycles. The *HyCARE* storage module logo and container are reported in Figure 2-16.

FIGURE 2-16 SCHEMATIC OF THE *HyCARE* SYSTEM¹⁴.

¹⁴ <https://hycare-project.eu/>

2.3 Electric energy storage comparison

HyCARE system can be initially compared with a classic Battery Energy Storage System (BESS). However, this analogy presents various criticisms and flaws that make the comparison misleading and not very sensible. Firstly, the engineering control of the two systems would have the electric vector as input and output, requiring for the *HyCARE* system, the refinement with an electrolysis and fuel cell system, with additional degrees of release that make it difficult to compare a unique solution for battery storage. Secondly, this comparison is limiting where it is not possible to valorize the exploitation of by-products of the processes (oxygen or heat as in the case of the H₂ use and production processes). Finally, for the sole purpose of accumulating the electric vector, the *HyCARE* solution (with the necessary auxiliaries) represents an unrealistic alternative due to the small size of the system which magnifies its economic aspects, which, however, scale rapidly with system size.

3. Assumptions and economic aspects

Each scenario comparison requires additional input parameters, other than the already exposed working regime assumptions (Table 2-3), to produce a quantitative analysis. Table 3-1 shows the main economic assumptions made.

TABLE 3-1: UTILITIES AND ECONOMIC ASSUMPTIONS.

Parameter	Value	Reference
U.S. Dollar to Euro conversion	0.92 €/USD	European Central Bank. ¹⁵
Cost of electricity	100 €/MWh	Average 2022 monthly electricity price in France. ¹⁶
Cost of water	2.96 €/m ³	Average price for residential user. ¹⁷
Cost of land	93 €/m ²	Average value of building land cost in different French regions, in 2018. ¹⁸
Cost of gaseous hydrogen	5 €/kg	Internal information.
Cost of DBT	3 €/kg	HySTOC, WP8, D8.3 A preliminary feasibility study. ⁹
Cost of DBT regeneration	1 €/kg _{DBT}	HySTOC, WP8, D8.3 A preliminary feasibility study. ⁹

A small introduction to economic KPI's listed in Table 2-2 is now presented, to explain how they are calculated in the present study. The CAPEX represents the capital expenditure required to purchase and install the system; the calculation method and the constituent parts are well detailed in *Subsection 3.1*. The OPEX represents the operational expenditure instead and it's composed by all the costs related to maintenance & repair, component substitution and utilities; the calculation method and the constituent parts are well detailed in *Subsection 3.2*. The total cost of ownership (TCO) represents the sum of CAPEX and OPEX over the period which has been chosen for the analysis (for this study, 30 yrs). The TCO can be calculated through Eq. 3.1.

$$TCO = CAPEX [\text{€}] + 30 \cdot OPEX \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{yr}} \right] \quad (3.1)$$

The last parameter is the levelized cost of storage (LCoS) and it is defined as the ratio between the TCO, and the amount of hydrogen stored and release over lifetime ($H_{2,tot}$). Two versions of these

¹⁵ https://www.ecb.europa.eu/stats/policy_and_exchange_rates/euro_reference_exchange_rates/html/eurofxref-graph-usd.en.html. Accessed 07.04.2022.

¹⁶ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1267546/france-monthly-wholesale-electricity-price/>

¹⁷ Internal information.

¹⁸ https://www.frenchproperty.com/news/french_property_market/building_plot_prices_2018#:~:text=The%20price%20of%20a%20building%20plot%20in%20France%20rose%20by,the%2011e%20Dde%20France.

parameters are calculated in this work: a non-actualised LCoS simply given by Eq. 3.2, and a more correct LCoS which is actualised over the system lifetime (Eq. 3.3).

$$LCoS \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kg}} \right] = \frac{TCO [\text{€}]}{H_{2,tot} [\text{kg}]} \quad (3.2)$$

$$LCoS \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kg}} \right] = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{30} TCO_i \cdot (1+r)^i}{\sum_{i=0}^{30} H_{2,i} \cdot (1+r)^i} \quad (3.3)$$

In Eq. 3.3, TCO_i and $H_{2,i}$ represent the TCO and the cumulative hydrogen release over the i -th year, respectively, while r represents the discount rate, which is set to 8% in the present analysis¹.

3.1 Capital expenditure

Capital expenditure consists of two main components:

- Direct capital cost, related to equipment supply and property purchase.
- Indirect capital cost, cost related to site preparation, engineering and design, contingencies, fees.

For all storage technologies has been considered an additional 30% of CAPEX as engineering cost.

3.1.1 Cost of equipment

One common way to evaluate the equipment purchasing cost is to use scaling laws. Knowing size S_0 and cost C_0 of a reference equipment, and the size S of the component to install, it's possible to estimate the cost of this latter. An example of scaling law is proposed in Eq. 3.4:

$$C_{uninst} = C_0 \cdot \left(\frac{S}{S_0} \right)^n \quad (3.4)$$

where n represents the scale exponent, which is characteristic of the technology. To estimate the cost of equipment, different studies and different cost data will be considered. Therefore, each cost will be related to its own reference year, in which it has been evaluated. For this reason, it's necessary to actualize all costs to a reference year, that for this study will be 2022. This is done thanks to the *Chemical Engineering Plant Cost Index* (CEPCI) and through Eq. 3.5, where the subscript *ref* represents the reference year of the study or the year in which the equipment cost has been evaluated.

$$C_{2022} = C_{ref} \cdot \frac{CEPCI_{2022}}{CEPCI_{ref}} \quad (3.5)$$

In the next subsections, the capital cost of each technology will be analyzed.

Gaseous hydrogen – 30 bar

As suggested by Figure 2-8, GH2-30 bar system includes only the storage vessel. For a low-pressure storage vessel, a constant specific uninstalled cost of 893,48 €₂₀₂₂/kg is used. This value came out considering some quotes from different vendors for low-pressure hydrogen storage systems. The installation factor proposed by *H2A Analysis Model* is equal to 1.3⁵.

Gaseous hydrogen – 350 bar

GH2-350 bar system includes the storage vessel and a 3-stages compressor, preliminary designed in *Subsection 2.1.2*. For a 350 bar tube trailer system, a constant specific uninstalled cost of 4667 €₂₀₂₂/kg is used. The installation factor proposed by *H2A Analysis Model* is equal to 1.3⁵.

Regarding the compressor, a 3-stage reciprocating cost function is provided by *H2A Analysis Model* and reported in Eq. 3.6, in which *Motor Rating* is estimated to be 110 percent of the compressor electric power demand⁵.

$$C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 23048 \cdot (Motor\ Rating\ [kWe])^{0.6089} \quad (3.6)$$

The installation factor proposed by *H2A Analysis Model* is equal to 1.3.

Liquid hydrogen

As suggested by Figure 2-11, the LH2 system includes a liquefaction section, a liquid hydrogen storage vessel and a regasification section.

Liquefaction of hydrogen is a large-scale technology, and no data are available for low production rates. Some literature cost functions have been considered and compared with literature cost data of single liquefiers. The results are plotted in Figure 3-1.

FIGURE 3-1: LH2 LIQUEFIER CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Several literature sources reported that, for hydrogen liquefaction plants, scaling exponents range from 0.6 to 0.7³. For this reason, the formula proposed by *Connelly et al.*¹⁹, which uses an exponent of 0.8, is not considered. Moreover, it could be noticed a good agreement between *Reuss et al.*¹ function and the one used in *H2A Analysis Model*⁵. The latter has been obtained through an interpolation of some vendor quotes collected and it is used for the present analysis. The scaling law is proposed in Eq. 3.7.

$$C_{inst} [\$_{2007}] = 8097193 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Flow}[\text{ton/day}])^{0.648} \quad (3.7)$$

For the LH2 storage vessel, some literature cost data and cost functions have been collected and are plotted in Figure 3-2. Moreover, an interpolation function has been obtained through the *MATLAB Optimization Toolbox*, based on the literature cost data collected.

FIGURE 3-2: LH2 VESSEL CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

As it can be seen in Figure 3-2, the interpolation function and the one used within the HySTOC project²⁰ show a similar behavior. Hence, the interpolation function will be used for the estimation of LH2 storage vessels (Eq. 3.8), based on their capacity.

¹⁹ E. Connelly, M. Penev, A. Elgowainy, C. Hunter, “Current Status of Hydrogen Liquefaction Costs”, DOE Hydrogen and Fuel Cells Program Record, 09.09.2019.

²⁰ Hydrogen Supply and Transportation using Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (HySTOC), WP8 Business Development and sustainability –Concept Studies, Economic Analysis, Life Cycle Assessment D8.5 A market analysis study. 2019.12.31.

$$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 4278 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity [kg]})^{0.609} \quad (3.8)$$

In conclusion, the capital expenditure of the LH2 vaporization system shows a great variability and uncertainty, as it is noticeable in Figure 3-3. Few cost data have been collected for LH2 vaporizers: in the *H2A Model Analysis*⁵ the authors distinguish between large-scale (terminal) and small-scale vaporizers, by assigning two different cost functions for the two different configurations. For about 250 kg/h there are two literature data. One matches the small scale model and the other is matching the large scale model.

FIGURE 3-3: LH2 VAPORIZER CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Considering high production rates, the “small-scale” equation overestimate vaporizers capital cost. On the contrary, at low production rates, the “large-scale” equation overestimate vaporizers capital cost. For this reason, the two equations proposed by *H2A Model Analysis*⁵ are used at the production rates (in kg/h) for which they were derived. More specifically, functions intersection is registered at a production rate of 101.7 kg/h, so the overall scaling law, used in the present study, is proposed in Eq. 3.9 and its trend is shown in Figure 3-4.

$$\begin{cases} C_{uninst} [\text{\$}_{2007}] = 900.87 \cdot \text{HydrogenFlow}[\text{kg/h}] + 2388.5 & \text{for } \dot{m} < 101.7 \\ C_{uninst} [\text{\$}_{2007}] = 111.39 \cdot \text{HydrogenFlow}[\text{kg/h}] + 82260 & \text{for } \dot{m} \geq 101.7 \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

FIGURE 3-4: LH2 VAPORIZER CAPITAL COST - ZOOM AT LOW PRODUCTION RATES.

Liquid organic hydrogen carriers

The LOHC system includes a hydrogenation unit, a storage vessel, and a dehydrogenation unit. Figure 3-5 shows some literature cost functions for the estimation of DBT hydrogenation units' capital cost. *Reuss et al.*¹ and the European project *HySTOC*²¹ used similar scaling law; in fact, both scaling equations use an exponent equal to 0.6. A single cost datum, that has been found for DBT hydrogenation systems (*Hydrogenious LOHC Technologies*), is reported in Figure 3-5 as a blue filled square. Moreover, other data have been found for methylcyclohexane (MCH) hydrogenation systems, which are depicted as empty red triangles²². Of course, different liquid organic hydrogen carriers are characterized by different operating conditions, such as pressure and temperature; however, the main components of the hydrogenation system will be strongly similar in both cases, as the process is the same. At small sizes, MCH cost data show a similar behavior to *Reuss et al.*¹ and *HySTOC*²¹, while they differ heavily at large sizes. This can be because MCH cost estimations consider the initial load of toluene and also the storage systems (one for toluene and one for MCH), unlike the *HySTOC* estimation. Both these aspects have a moderate influence at low production rates, while they have a great influence at high production rates, causing MCH data and *HySTOC* function to diverge.

²¹ Hydrogen Supply and Transportation using Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (HySTOC), WP8 Business Development and sustainability –Concept Studies, Economic Analysis, Life Cycle Assessment D8.6 Final feasibility study. 2020.06.30.

²² D.D. Papadias, R.K. Ahluwalia, "Toluene-MCH as a Two-Way Carrier for Hydrogen Transmission and Storage". U.S. DOE Hydrogen and Fuel Cells Program. 2020 Annual Merit Review and Peer Evaluation Meeting, Washington D.C., 30.05.2020.

FIGURE 3-5: LOHC HYDROGENATION CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Considering all these aspects, the cost functions proposed for the *HySTOC*²¹ project, reported in Eq. 3.10, is used to estimate the capital cost of DBT hydrogenation plants.

$$C_{inst}[\text{€}_{2019}] = 8 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{HydrogenFlow}[\text{ton/day}]}{12} \right)^{0.6} \quad (3.10)$$

The same approach has been used for the dehydrogenations system. Figure 3-6 shows three literature cost functions (the same reported previously for the hydrogenation system), a single cost datum for a DBT dehydrogenation unit and some cost data for MCH dehydrogenation units.

FIGURE 3-6: LOHC DEHYDROGENATION CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

Also in this case, it can be noticed how, at large sizes, *HySTOC*²¹ function and MCH data differs significantly, but less than for the hydrogenation system (Figure 3-5). This is because, this time, the storage system is considered in MCH data, while the initial load of MCH is not. Again, *HySTOC* scaling law will be used for the estimation of the DBT dehydrogenation system (Eq. 3.11).

$$C_{inst}[\text{€}_{2019}] = 3.5 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Hydrogen Flow [ton/day]}}{1.5} \right)^{0.6} \quad (3.11)$$

In conclusion, two storage systems are required to store both the DBT, at low hydrogen content, required for the hydrogenation phase and the DBT, hydrogen enriched, required for the dehydrogenation phase. Each one of these storage systems will be considered as a conventional gasoline/diesel tank, due to the chemical similarities between the two fuels and the LOHC⁸. Regarding fuel tanks, some vendor data have been collected and compared to some literature cost functions. Moreover, an interpolation function, based on the collected literature cost data, has been obtained through the *MATLAB Optimization Toolbox*. Results are shown in Figure 3-7: LOHC storage vessel capital cost - literature analysis.

FIGURE 3-7: LOHC STORAGE VESSEL CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

At low capacities, the interpolation, *Perry's*²³ and *Hurskainen's*²⁴ functions show similar trends. However, all these three functions have different scaling exponents: 0.7175 for the interpolation, 0.77 for *Hurskainen's* and 0.57 for *Perry's*.

Figure 3-8 shows the behavior, at both small and large sizes, of the cost functions analyzed.

FIGURE 3-8: LOHC STORAGE VESSEL CAPITAL COST – LITERATURE ANALYSIS PT.2.

²³ Perry, R. H., & Green, D. W. (2008). *Perry's chemical engineers' handbook*. New York: McGraw-Hill.

²⁴ Hurskainen, M., & Itonen, J. (2020). Techno-economic feasibility of road transport of hydrogen using liquid organic hydrogen carriers. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 45(56), 32098 -32112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2020.08.186>

LOHC Storage Vessel Capital Cost

The interpolation function and *Perry*'s one show similar trends at low capacities, while they diverge at higher ones. A good agreement is maintained between the interpolation function and *Hurskainen*'s one also at high storage capacities. In this study, the interpolation function is chosen to estimate the DBT storage vessel capital expenditure (Eq. 3.12).

$$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 123.4 \cdot (\text{HydrogenCapacity}[\text{kg}])^{0.7175} \quad (3.12)$$

The installation factor chosen for the storage vessel is equal to 1.3, consistent with what has been done for the other storage technologies.

Finally, the initial load of DBT should be considered. Knowing the cost of DBT and its gravimetric capacity, it's possible to evaluate the cost of the DBT required to store a specific amount of hydrogen.

Metal hydrides

For the metal hydride storage system, the cost estimation will be carried out considering a single storage vessel, comprehensive of metal hydride pellets, heat-exchange section, and the tank itself. At very low sizes, lots of cost data can be collected from online stores (*Fuel Cell Store*²⁵ and *Hydrogen Components Inc.*²⁶), while from medium to large size few data are available.

Figure 3-9 shows some literature cost data and the trend of a couple of literature cost functions.

FIGURE 3-9: METAL HYDRIDE SYSTEM CAPITAL COST - LITERATURE ANALYSIS.

²⁵ <https://www.fuelcellstore.com/>

²⁶ <https://www.hydrogencomponents.com/hydride.html>

Both the considered cost functions show a similar trend at medium sizes, even if *Ganda et al.*²⁷ proposed a scaling exponent of 0.7509 while *Amos et al.*³ proposed a constant specific CAPEX (scaling exponent equal to 1). At large sizes, only a cost datum has been found and it's fairly predicted by *Ganda's* scaling law. The latter shows a good consistency with literature data also at small and medium size, as it is possible to see in

FIGURE 3-10: METAL HYDRIDE SYSTEM CAPITAL COST - SMALL TO MEDIUM SIZES.

²⁷ F. Ganda, G. Maronati, "Economic Data and Modeling Support for the Two Regional Case Studies", Nuclear Science Engineering Division, Argonne National Laboratory, August 2018.

Considering all these aspects, the cost function proposed by *Ganda et al.* (Eq. 3.13) is used for the cost assessment of metal hydride storage systems.

$$C_{inst}[\text{€}_{2021}] = 13744 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity [kg]})^{0.7509} \quad (3.13)$$

The metal hydride storage system needs a further consideration, because of the different life expectancy of the storage vessel and the metal hydride pellets, how it will be explained in *Section 3.2* (
(

Table 3-5). For this reason, the overall system cost must be split into the metal pellet and the vessel ones, to estimate the equipment substitution costs. For simplicity's sake, the vessel cost (comprehensive of heat-exchange section) will be considered equal to the 40% of the total system cost, for all sizes²⁸.

The installation factor chosen for the storage vessel is equal to 1.3, consistent with what has been done for the other storage technologies.

HyCARE

HyCARE system's capital expenditure is evaluated thanks to the information given by the project partners. However, *HyCARE* information have a high accuracy compared to other system ones (e.g., costs of valves, insulation and all BoP components, labor, and assembly cost). For this reason, a simple sum of all costs will penalize *HyCARE*. Therefore, the method used consists in considering only the main components' cost (alloy pellets, storage tanks, PCM modules and solar heating panels) and to multiply them for an installing factor and engineering cost like other technologies one (IF equal to 1.3).

Regarding the system scale-up, the solution used for the storage of 40 kgH₂ is considered modular, because the whole system is containerized. A fundamental aspect to take in consideration in that the readiness level of the *HyCARE* system is not as high as the ones of some other technologies. For example, for the gaseous hydrogen storage there are lots of companies which produce storage tanks or cylinders, even at very high production rates. On the contrary, the *HyCARE* system is an innovative solution, which has been produced at very low production rates (single unit). It is well-known that the cost of a single unit is a function of the production rate: the higher the production volume, the lower the specific cost. In general, as the production quantity increases, manufacturing cost decreases in a predictable manner²⁹. One common way to evaluate this aspect is through the cumulative average theory, which provides that every time the production is doubled, the average cost required to produce a group of n unit decreases by a constant percentage²⁹. The technological learning can be expressed through a power function (Eq. 3.14) in which *capex* represents the specific capital expenditure, a the specific capital cost of a unitary capacity, X the total cumulative capacity and b the learning elasticity³⁰.

$$capex [\text{€/kg}] = a \cdot X^b \quad (3.14)$$

In the usual case where b is negative, it's possible to define the learning rate l_r as expressed in Eq. 3.15. The learning rate represents the percentage decrease of specific capital cost for each doubling of cumulative production volume.

²⁸ Assumptions based on internal information on some systems.

²⁹ N.F. Brown, T.P. Anderson, "Learning Rate Sensitivity Model", The Aerospace Corporation, 2018 NASA Cost and Schedule Symposium. August 14-16, 2018.

³⁰ McDonald, A. and Schrattenholzer, L. (2002) 'Learning curves and technology assessment', Int. J. Technology Management, Vol. 23, Nos. 7/8, pp.718-745.

$$l_r = 1 - 2^b \quad (3.15)$$

Each technology is characterized by a proper learning elasticity and, consequently, by a proper learning rate. Starting from CAPEX data provided by *HyCARE* partners Stuehff, Tecnodelta and GKN, each for the part of its competence, these data were fitted using the learning rate equation, to find the learning elasticity of a typical solid-state storage technology. The results obtained are plotted in

Figure 3-11.

FIGURE 3-11: HyCARE LEARNING CURVE

The learning curve equation, obtained through the *OriginLab software*, has a learning elasticity of -0.09436. For the *HyCARE* system, the same exponent will be used, while *HyCARE* baseline specific capital cost will be used to calculate the constant a . The overall learning equation that will be used to assess the market penetration of *HyCARE* system is reported in Eq. 3.16.

$$capex_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2022}/kg] = 16330.61 \cdot X^{-0.09436} \quad (3.16)$$

To sum up, each *HyCARE* module can contain up to 40 kg of hydrogen. Each unit's specific capital cost is scaled according to the production volume and the learning rate, as proposed in Eq. 3.14 (e.g., if the storage capacity requested is 120 kg of hydrogen, the specific capital cost of each unit is obtained using $X = 3$ in Eq. 3.14).

Chillers and heat pumps

Some components require the presence of a cooling device (e.g., GH2-350 bar compressor, LOHC hydrogenation unit, metal hydride absorption) and a heating one (e.g., LOHC dehydrogenation unit, metal hydride desorption). Hence, it is important to assess how the capital expenditure of these

devices impact the whole system cost. *Popovski et al.*³¹ presented the investment costs associated with a compression chiller and with an air source heat pump, in €₂₀₁₅/kW_{th}. These assumptions are reported in Table 3-2 and used in the present study.

TABLE 3-2: HEAT PUMP AND CHILLER ECONOMIC ASSUMPTIONS³¹.

Equipment	Specific investment cost
Compression chiller	650 [€ ₂₀₁₅ /kW _{th}]
Air source heat pump	700 [€ ₂₀₁₅ /kW _{th}]

3.1.2 Property purchase cost

An important aspect to consider is the storage land occupation. In fact, by not considering it, low pressure gaseous storage solutions could result the most cost-effective options, due to low compression energy requirements and low vessels capital cost. Of course, one of the advantages of storing hydrogen in other forms is to reduce the space occupied by the storage system. In the next subsections, each storage system footprint will be estimated. The footprint of chillers and heat pumps, if present, is expected to have little influence on the whole systems footprint; hence, it has been neglected.

Gaseous hydrogen – 30 bar

The GH2-30 bar tank consists of consists of an accumulation cylinder with hemispherical ends, having the same diameter and thickness as the low-pressure tanks quoted by tank manufacturer. The cylinder has hemispherical ends, an external diameter ϕ_{out} of 2.5 m and a wall thickness t of 0.020 m. The cylinder's length L is assumed equal to 7 meters, provide by cylinders' vendor³². The capacity of the single storage tank at 30 bar is calculated starting from the formula of the volume of a cylinder with hemispherical ends, as per (Eq. 3.17) and multiplying by the density of the gas at the desired conditions (Eq. 3.18). At 25 °C and 30 bar, the hydrogen density ρ is 2.397 kg/m³³³ and the stored capacity of the single H₂ tank at 30 bar is equal to 69.95 kg.

$$V [m^3] = \pi r_{in}^2 l + \frac{4}{3} \pi r_{in}^3 \quad (3.17)$$

with

r_{in} : internal cylinder radius;

³¹ Eftim Popovski, Tobias Fleiter, Hugo Santos, Vitor Leal, Eduardo Oliveira Fernandes, Technical and economic feasibility of sustainable heating and cooling supply options in southern European municipalities-A case study for Matosinhos, Portugal, Energy, Volume 153, 2018, Pages 311-323, ISSN 0360-5442, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.04.036>.

³² Internal information.

³³ NIST Chemistry WebBook. <https://webbook.nist.gov/cgi/cbook.cgi?ID=1333-74-0>

L : total tank length including hemispherical ends;

D : internal diameter of hemispherical ends;

l : cylindrical part length = $L - D$;

For greater clarity, we report in Figure 3-12 the cylindrical tank with hemispherical ends.

FIGURE 3-12: CYLINDRICAL TANK WITH HEMISPHERICAL ENDS

$$H_2 \text{ Capacity [kg]} = \rho * V \quad (3.18)$$

The safety distances for gaseous hydrogen systems can be obtained through a risk analysis of the systems themselves; however, the risk assessment is not the purpose of this work. For this reason, literature general safety distance will be used. *Houssin et al.*³⁴ stated that a safety distance of 8 m between public domain and gaseous hydrogen source is required (i.e., safety external distance). The *HyLaw Online Database*³⁵ contains the actual permitting requirements and safety distances for gas, liquid, and metal hydride stationary storage systems, for several European Countries. In France, an external safety distance of 8 m and an internal safety distance of 5 m are required. If the storage unit overcome the capacity of 1000 kg of hydrogen, the operator must produce a “safety & risk analysis” and an “environmental impact analysis”. In this study, it’s assumed that the same storage unit can store up to 1000 kg of hydrogen: if the total hydrogen overcomes this upper limit, another storage unit is required, and it’s placed near the former one with a distance equal to the internal safety distance. No information has been collected about the distance required between two hydrogen vessels. Hence, 50 cm is set as the minimum distance required for cylinders inspection. Furthermore, it has been assumed that the tanks are installed in a vertical position.

³⁴ Deborah Houssin, Sile Brennan, Tom Van Esbroeck, Didier Bouix, “Report on hydrogen safety aspects of technologies, systems and infrastructures pertinent to responders”, HyResponder Deliverable D1.1, 30-06-2020.

³⁵ <https://www.hylaw.eu/>

Gaseous hydrogen – 350 bar

The GH2-350 bar storage system consists of storage cylinders with an internal diameter ϕ_{in} of 0.5 m, a wall thickness of 0.071 m and a 25.30 length. By applying the same equations of the tank at 30 bar, described above in equations 3.17 and 3.18 and considering that at 25 °C and 350 bar, the density of hydrogen is 23.315 kg/m³, a quantity of H₂ stored in each tank at 350 bar equal to 114.40 kg.

Moreover, also the presence of the compression system needs to be included. The footprint of different hydrogen compressors has been collected from literature, and it's presented in Figure 3-12 as a function of the hydrogen mass flow. The function proposed to estimate the footprint of the hydrogen compressor is reported in Eq. 3.19.

$$FP_{comp} [m^2] = 2.023 \cdot (Hydrogen\ Flow[kg/h])^{0.5259} \quad (3.19)$$

FIGURE 3-12: HYDROGEN COMPRESSOR FOOTPRINT ANALYSIS.

The internal and external safety distances adopted are the same used for the GH2-30 bar system. Moreover, every 1000 kg of hydrogen stored, an additional storage unit is required, placed at a distance equal to the internal safety distance. The distance between compressor system and storage system is the internal safety distance. No information has been collected about the distance required between two hydrogen vessels. Hence, 50 cm is set as the minimum distance required for cylinders inspection.

Liquid hydrogen

The liquid hydrogen solution is composed of the liquefaction and regasification unit and the storage system. The vaporizer is expected to have little influence on the whole system footprint, both at small and large sizes. Moreover, no data have been found to estimate vaporizers footprint. For these reasons, the land occupation of vaporizers will not be considered. The *Hydrogen Delivery Scenario Analysis Model*³⁶ proposed a scaling law to assess the footprint of a liquefier. This function is reported in Eq. 3.20.

$$FP_{liq}[m^2] = 25000 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Hydrogen Flow}[\text{ton/day}]}{30} \right)^{0.6} \quad (3.20)$$

Regarding the liquid hydrogen storage system, a spherical vessel is considered. The diameter of the sphere is assumed to scale-up according to the storage capacity (Eq. 3.21), while the wall thickness is set to 0.02 m, according to some cryogenic vessel data³⁷. A LH2 density of 67.71 kg/m³ is used for the calculation (2 bar and -250 °C)³³.

$$\phi_{out} = 2t + \sqrt[3]{\frac{6 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg]}{\pi \cdot \rho}} \quad (3.21)$$

The *HyLaw Online Database*³⁵ gives a storage external safety distance of 20 m for liquid hydrogen. No rules or prescription are detected between liquid hydrogen storage systems; therefore, no storage upper limit is considered.

Liquid organic hydrogen carriers

The LOHC solution consists of the hydrogenation system, the dehydrogenation system, and the storage unit. The footprint of both hydrogenation and dehydrogenation units is difficult to evaluate, because of the poverty of data in literature. Considering that both units are large sections with lots of balance of plant components, their footprint has been estimated through the same function proposed for the liquefaction unit in Eq. 3.20.

As for the storage system, a spherical shape vessel is used to store the DBT. The wall thickness is set to 6 mm, in comparison with typical diesel/gasoline vessel thickness³⁸. The sphere diameter is calculated, as a function of the storage capacity, through Eq. 3.22, where ρ_{DBT} is the density of DBT and "wt"_{H₂} is the hydrogen gravimetric capacity.

³⁶ https://www.hydrogen.energy.gov/h2a_delivery.html

³⁷ <https://www.lindedirect.com/resources/safety-information/cryogenic-tank-safety>

³⁸ <https://www.emilianaserbatoi.com/en-ww/search.aspx?fti=tank+fuel+thickness>

$$\phi_{out} = 2t + \sqrt[3]{\frac{6 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Capacity [kg]}}{\pi \cdot \rho_{DBT} \cdot w_{H_2}}} \quad (3.22)$$

No rules or prescription are detected for liquid organic hydrogen carrier systems. Due to the low hazard of these systems, no storage upper limits were assumed and an external safety distance equal to the 30% of the one required for gaseous compressed systems was considered, so equal to 2.4 m.

Metal hydrides

Values related to 3 different systems produced by *GKN HYDROGEN*³⁹ have been collected and used to create a scaling law to estimate the footprint of metal hydride storage systems as a function of their capacities. Figure 3-13 shows the obtained results and the interpolation function is described in Eq. 3.23.

$$FP_{MH} [m^2] = 2.799 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity [kg]})^{0.3332} \quad (3.23)$$

FIGURE 3-13: METAL HYDRIDE FOOTPRINT ANALYSIS.

No rules or prescription are reported for metal hydride storage systems, infact no information about this storage technology are reported in DM 23/10/2018⁴⁰. Due to the low hazard of these systems and to the information provided by a metal hydrides manufacturer (GKN), the authors assume no storage

³⁹ <https://www.gknhydrogen.com/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2018/11/05/18A07049/sg>

upper limit and an external safety distance equal to the 30% of the one required for gaseous compressed systems, equal to 2.4 m.

HyCARE

The *HyCARE* system is a modular system, in which all the equipment required to store 40 kg of hydrogen is contained in a standard container with dimensions 6.5 x 2.4 x 2.2 m³ (L x W x H). The external safety distance between two containers is assumed to be 30% of the one required for gaseous compressed systems.

3.1.3 Indirect capital costs

Indirect capital costs can be estimated as a percentage of the total capital uninstalled cost. Table 3-3 shows indirect cost percentages estimated for refueling hydrogen station components in the *H2A Analysis Model*⁵. The same percentages of the purchase cost are assumed in the present study. The overall percentage originates what is called installation factor *IF*.

TABLE 3-3: INDIRECT CAPITAL COST AS A PERCENTAGE OF PURCHASE COST⁵.

Parameter	Value
Site preparation	5%
Design	10%
Project contingency	5%
One-time licensing fees	0%
Up-front permitting costs	3%
Overall installation factor	1.23

For this reason, the total installed component cost can be expressed through Eq. 3.24. To be conservative, an installation factor of 1.3 was chosen.

$$C_{inst} = C_0 \cdot \left(\frac{S}{S_0}\right)^n \cdot IF \quad (3.24)$$

Some cost functions will already include the installation factor, while other will not.

Table 3-4 shows the *IF* adopted for each equipment.

TABLE 3-4: INSTALLATION FACTORS FOR ALL EQUIPMENT.

Equipment	Installation factor (IF)
GH2-30 bar storage vessel	1.3
GH2-350 bar storage vessel	1.3

GH2-350 3-stages reciprocating compressor	1.3
LH2 liquefaction unit	Already considered in the scaling law
LH2 storage vessel	1.3
LH2 vaporization unit	1.3
LOHC hydrogenation unit	Already considered in the scaling law
LOHC storage vessel	1.3
LOHC dehydrogenation unit	Already considered in the scaling law
Metal hydride system	1.3
Heat pump	1.3
Chiller	1.3

3.2 Operational expenditure

The operational expenditure (OPEX) is related to equipment maintenance, its substitution over plant lifetime and the costs associated with utilities. As to maintenance and utilities costs, they will be discussed within each subsection dedicated to the description of each storage technology. On the contrary, the methodology to evaluate equipment substitution will be discussed in the following lines. Different components are characterized by different lifetimes and, therefore, by a different number of substitutions over the considered plant lifetime.

Table 3-5 shows the lifetime assumptions made for all the subcomponents considered in this study.

TABLE 3-5: COMPONENTS' LIFETIME ASSUMPTIONS.

Equipment	Lifetime [yr]	Reference
GH2-30 bar storage vessel	20	<i>Reuss et al.</i> ¹ <i>Teichmann et al.</i> ⁴¹
GH2-350 bar storage vessel	20	<i>Reuss et al.</i> ¹ <i>Teichmann et al.</i> ⁴¹
GH2-350 3-stages reciprocating compressor	15	<i>Hydrogen Delivery Scenario Analysis Model.</i> ³⁶
LH2 liquefaction unit	40	<i>Connelly et al.</i> ¹⁹
LH2 storage vessel	20	<i>Reuss et al.</i> ¹ <i>Teichmann et al.</i> ⁴¹
LH2 vaporization unit	15	<i>Hydrogen Delivery Scenario Analysis Model.</i> ³⁵
LOHC hydrogenation unit	20	<i>HySTOC, WP8, D8.6 Final feasibility study.</i> ²¹
LOHC storage vessel	20	<i>Reuss et al.</i> ¹ <i>Teichmann et al.</i> ⁴¹
LOHC dehydrogenation unit	20	<i>HySTOC, WP8, D8.6 Final feasibility study.</i> ²¹
Metal hydride tank	20 ⁴²	GKN Hydrogen.
Metal hydride pellets	30	Internal information.
Heat Pump	20	<i>Popovski et al.</i> ³¹
Chiller	20	<i>Popovski et al.</i> ³¹

The depreciation of each equipment, over its lifetime $L_{f,eq}$, will be evaluated through the *Modified Accelerated Cost Recovery System (MACRS)*, which has been adopted also for the *Hydrogen Delivery Scenario Analysis Model*³⁶. Table 3-6 shows the depreciation rates (MACRS) for different components' lifetimes.

⁴¹ Daniel Teichmann, Wolfgang Arlt, Peter Wasserscheid, Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers as an efficient vector for the transport and storage of renewable energy, *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, Volume 37, Issue 23, 2012, Pages 18118-18132, ISSN 0360-3199, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2012.08.066>.

⁴² As reported by GKN hydrogen.

TABLE 3-6: MACRS DEPRECIATION RATES ADOPTED⁴³.

Year	Depreciation rate for recovery period					
	3-year	5-year	7-year	10-year	15-year	20-year
1	33,33%	20,00%	14,29%	10,00%	5,00%	3,750%
2	44,45%	32,00%	24,49%	18,00%	9,50%	7,219%
3	14,81%	19,20%	17,49%	14,40%	8,55%	6,677%
4	7,41%	11,52%	12,49%	11,52%	7,70%	6,177%
5		11,52%	8,93%	9,22%	6,93%	5,713%
6		5,76%	8,92%	7,37%	6,23%	5,285%
7			8,93%	6,55%	5,90%	4,888%
8			4,46%	6,55%	5,90%	4,522%
9				6,56%	5,91%	4,462%
10				6,55%	5,90%	4,461%
11				3,28%	5,91%	4,462%
12					5,90%	4,461%
13					5,91%	4,462%
14					5,90%	4,461%
15					5,91%	4,462%
16					2,95%	4,461%
17						4,462%
18						4,461%
19						4,462%
20						4,461%
21						2,231%

The lifetime used for the comparison of all storage options $L_{f,pl}$ has been set to 30 years (Table 2-3). So, it's possible that, at the 30th year of operation, some components (maybe recently substituted) have still a high remaining service life and, therefore, a high useful value. The remaining service life R_{lf} of a component can be obtained through Eq. 3.25, where N represents the number of substitutions over lifetime required for the specific component.

$$R_{lf}[yr] = (N + 1) \cdot L_{f,eq} - L_{f,pl} \tag{3.25}$$

Once that the component remaining service life has been calculated, it is possible to know its depreciated remaining value just using the depreciation rates given in Table 3-6. One exception is done for the liquefier, whose service life exceeds 20 years. Therefore, a simplified approach will be adopted, in which the depreciation period for the liquefier will be considered equal to 20 years. In

⁴³ Internal Revenue Service (IRS), "How to Depreciate Property", Department of the Treasury, Publication 946 Cat. No. 13081F, 2021.

this way, the depreciated value of the liquefier, after 20 years of operation, will be equal to the salvage value. In other words, the depreciated value of the liquefier will be maintained constant from the 21st year to the 30th year. For all the components, the salvage value is assumed to be the 10% of the initial installed equipment cost.

In the next subsections, each storage system will be explored to estimate its operational expenditure.

Gaseous hydrogen – 30 bar

No utilities are required for the continuous operation of the GH2-30 bar system. The only O&M costs are those relative to system maintenance and its substitution over plant lifetime. Gaseous hydrogen storage maintenance is assumed to be 1% of CAPEX on yearly base²⁷.

Gaseous hydrogen – 350 bar

For GH2-350 bar there are not only maintenance and substitution costs, but also those related to the use of electrical energy to drive the compressor and to the discharged gas cooling. The former can be computed knowing the electricity cost and the electrical power demand of the compressor. The overall theoretical power required for the compression can be calculated through Eq. 3.26:

$$P_{comp} = Q \cdot \frac{Z T R}{MM \cdot \eta} \cdot \frac{n \gamma}{\gamma - 1} \cdot \left[\left(\frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \right)^{\frac{\gamma-1}{n \gamma}} - 1 \right] \quad (3.26)$$

where Q is the hydrogen mass flow rate, Z the compressibility factor, MM the molecular mass, R the ideal gas constant, T the absolute inlet temperature, η the compressor efficiency, n the number of compressor stages, γ the diatomic constant factor, P_{in} and P_{out} the inlet and outlet pressure, respectively⁴⁴. The motor efficiency ε_m is calculated via Eq. 3.27, in which ξ represents the natural logarithm of the shaft power (expressed in kW)⁵.

$$\varepsilon_m = 8 \cdot 10^{-5} \xi^4 - 0.0015 \xi^3 + 0.0061 \xi^2 + 0.0311 \xi + 0.7617 \quad (3.27)$$

The latter, instead, can be evaluated knowing hydrogen flow and temperature rise and some specifications about the cooling system. In each stage the inlet temperature is assumed to be 37.8 °C, as previously stated, while the outlet temperature can be calculated through Eq. 2.2 and it's common to all stages because all the stage compression ratios are equal. The water required to cool the discharge gas is assumed to be produced through a chiller with an EER of 2.5. The costs of pumping water are neglected. Hence, the electric power required to produce the cooling water, for the 3-stage cooling (2 intercoolers and 1 aftercooler), can be evaluated thanks to Eq. 3.28, where $h_{j,H2}^{in}$ and $h_{j,H2}^{out}$

⁴⁴ C. van Leeuwen, "Report on the costs involved with PtG technologies and their potentials across EU", STORE&GO WP8, 30.04.2018.

are the j -th stage inlet and outlet hydrogen specific enthalpy, \dot{m}_{H_2} the hydrogen mass flow and n the overall number of stages. Enthalpy is evaluated through the *NIST Chemistry WebBook*³³.

$$P_{el} = \frac{\dot{m}_{H_2}}{EER} \cdot \sum_{j=1}^n (h_{j,H_2}^{in} - h_{j,H_2}^{out}) \quad (3.28)$$

Gaseous hydrogen storage maintenance is assumed to be 1% of CAPEX and compressor maintenance is assumed to be 4% of CAPEX, both on yearly base²⁷.

Liquid hydrogen

For LH2 system, O&M costs consist mainly of equipment maintenance and substitution over lifetime and electricity, both for liquefaction and vaporization. Liquefaction cost is the heaviest operational cost, and it depends on the size of the system. Figure 3-14 shows some vendors data collected for the *H2A Analysis Model*⁵ and the interpolation function obtained.

FIGURE 3-14: LIQUEFACTION UNIT ENERGY REQUIREMENT⁵.

In general, liquefaction energy demand varies from 8-13 kWh/kg of produced hydrogen^{1,3,27}. However, the interpolation function proposed by *H2A Analysis Model*⁵ could overestimate the energy required for little sizes, because it has been obtained through cost data of large size plants. For this reason, the author’s decision is to keep a constant energy demand under a size threshold. Hence, the function obtained can be expressed with the following system of equations (Eq. 3.29), in which P_{el} represents the specific power consumption (in kWh/kg) and \dot{m} the hydrogen flow (in kg/h).

$$\begin{cases} P_{el} = 17.844 \cdot \left(\frac{24 \cdot \dot{m}}{1000}\right)^{-0.1548} & \text{for } \dot{m} \geq 127.9 \text{ kg/h} \\ P_{el} = 15 & \text{for } \dot{m} < 127.9 \text{ kg/h} \end{cases} \quad (3.29)$$

In general, evaporation cost is estimated to be negligible compared to liquefaction one. No relevant data are available on the energy consumption for the vaporization unit. For this reason, vaporization energy consumption is assumed to be constant for all sizes and equal to 0.6 kWh/kg¹. On yearly base, liquid hydrogen storage maintenance is assumed to be 1% of CAPEX, liquefier maintenance 4% of CAPEX and vaporizer maintenance 1% of CAPEX^{27,45}.

Liquid organic hydrogen carriers

O&M costs consist mainly of equipment maintenance and substitution over lifetime, hydrogenation and dehydrogenation units electric demand, dehydrogenation heating and hydrogenation cooling requirements, LOHC regeneration. The cooling demand is assumed to be provided by a refrigeration unit (EER=2.5), while the heat of dehydrogenation is obtained through a heat pump (COP=3), as previously stated. Moreover, during each charge-discharge cycle a small amount of DBT is lost: this amount is assumed to be regenerated through distillation. Table 3-7 shows the assumptions made for all these operational aspects.

TABLE 3-7: LOHC O&M ASSUMPTIONS.

Parameter	Value	Reference
Hydrogenation electric demand	0.37 kWh/kgH ₂	Reuss et al. ¹
Dehydrogenation electric demand	0.37 kWh/kgH ₂	Reuss et al. ¹
Hydrogenation cooling demand	8.90 kWh/kgH ₂	Reuss et al. ¹
Dehydrogenation heating demand	8.90 kWh/kgH ₂	Reuss et al. ¹
DBT loss per cycle	0.013 % _{wl,DBT}	HySTOC, WP4, D4.1 Decision on LOHC storage and logistics concept. ⁴⁶

On yearly base, hydrogenation and dehydrogenation maintenances are assumed to be 1.5% and 3% of CAPEX, respectively²¹. LOHC storage maintenance is set as 1% of CAPEX, due to technology similarity with other storage technologies (gaseous compressed and liquid hydrogen vessels).

⁴⁵ Integrated Design for Demonstration of Efficient Liquefaction of Hydrogen (idealhy), WP3 Whole Chain Assessment, D3.16 Hydrogen Liquefaction Report. 2016-12-16.

⁴⁶ Hydrogen Supply and Transportation using Liquid Organic Hydrogen Carriers (HySTOC), WP4 – LOHC logistics infrastructures, D4.1 Decision on LOHC storage and logistics concept. 2018-06-30.

Metal hydrides

For metal hydride system, O&M costs consist mainly of equipment maintenance and substitution over lifetime, heating/cooling for hydrogen desorption/absorption and metal alloy activation process. Table 3-8 shows the assumptions made, assuming to use the same alloy (TiFe-based compound) used for the *HyCARE*¹⁴ project.

TABLE 3-8: METAL HYDRIDE O&M ASSUMPTIONS.

Parameter	Value	Reference
Number of activation cycles	5	<i>HyCARE</i> , WP3, D3.2 Characterisation of powder and pellets ⁴⁷ .
Enthalpy of absorption	-29.6 kJ/molH ₂	<i>HyCARE</i> , WP3, D3.2 Characterisation of powder and pellets ⁴⁷ .
Enthalpy of desorption	+30.2 kJ/molH ₂	<i>HyCARE</i> , WP3, D3.2 Characterisation of powder and pellets ⁴⁷ .

The heating power will be provided through a heat pump (COP=3), while the cooling power with a chiller (EER=2.5). On yearly base, MH tank maintenance is assumed to be 1.5% of CAPEX⁴⁸.

HyCARE

All electricity consumption, maintenance costs, the number and maintenance costs were punctually provided by the suppliers of the various subsystems as per Table 3-9.

TABLE 3-9: OPEX FOR HYCARE SYSTEM⁴⁹.

Integrated system section	OPEX [€/yr]
Vessel (+HX)	3600
Alloy pellets	2322
PCM	-
Thermal solar panel	-
Electricity, heating, and cooling	87.6

The other OPEX relating to the container ventilation system and the automation and control system have not been considered in order not to penalize the *HyCARE* system compared to other storage technologies in which such contributions are not estimated.

⁴⁷ Erika Michela Dematteis, Fermin Cuevas, & Michel Latroche. (2021). Characterisation of powder and pellets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4638519>

⁴⁸ Internal information.

⁴⁹ Provided by *HyCARE* Partners.

Chillers and heat pumps

The electric energy required for the operation of both the heat pump and chiller can be calculating knowing the heating/cooling demand and their efficiency, in terms of COP and EER. On yearly base, heat pump and chiller maintenances are assumed to be 1% of CAPEX³¹.

3.3 Cost summary

To sum up the main assumptions made in the previous section, two summary tables are proposed:

Equipment	Cost function	Reference
GH2-30 bar storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 893,48 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg]$	
GH2-350 bar storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2017}] = 4667 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg]$	50
GH2-350 3-stages reciprocating compressor	$C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 23048 \cdot (\text{Motor Rating} [kWe])^{0.6089}$	5
LH2 liquefaction unit	$C_{inst} [\$_{2007}] = 8097193 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Flow} [ton/day])^{0.648}$	5
LH2 storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 4278 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg])^{0.609}$	20
LH2 vaporization unit	$\begin{cases} C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 900.87 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Flow} [kg/h] + 2388.5 \\ C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 111.39 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Flow} [kg/h] + 82260 \end{cases}$	5
LOHC hydrogenation unit	$C_{inst} [\text{€}_{2019}] = 8 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Hydrogen Flow} [ton/day]}{12} \right)^{0.6}$	20
LOHC storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 123.4 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg])^{0.7175}$	24
LOHC dehydrogenation unit	$C_{inst} [\text{€}_{2015}] = 3.5 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Hydrogen Flow} [ton/day]}{1.5} \right)^{0.6}$	20
Metal hydride system	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 13744 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg])^{0.7509}$	27
Heat pump	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2015}] = 700 \cdot \text{HeatingDemand} [kW_{th}]$	31

Chiller	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2015}] = 650 \cdot \text{CoolingDemand}[\text{kW}_{th}]$	31
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for CAPEX cost functions and

Table 3-10 for maintenance costs. For the operational costs related to utilities, please refer to Section 3.2.

TABLE 3-9: SUMMARY OF CAPEX COST FUNCTION ADOPTED.

Equipment	Cost function	Reference
GH2-30 bar storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 893,48 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg]$	50
GH2-350 bar storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2017}] = 4667 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg]$	50
GH2-350 3-stages reciprocating compressor	$C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 23048 \cdot (\text{Motor Rating} [kWe])^{0.6089}$	5
LH2 liquefaction unit	$C_{inst} [\$_{2007}] = 8097193 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Flow} [\text{ton/day}])^{0.648}$	5
LH2 storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 4278 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg])^{0.609}$	20
LH2 vaporization unit	$\begin{cases} C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 900.87 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Flow} [kg/h] + 2388.5 \\ C_{uninst} [\$_{2007}] = 111.39 \cdot \text{Hydrogen Flow} [kg/h] + 82260 \end{cases}$	5
LOHC hydrogenation unit	$C_{inst} [\text{€}_{2019}] = 8 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Hydrogen Flow} [\text{ton/day}]}{12} \right)^{0.6}$	20
LOHC storage vessel	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 123.4 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg])^{0.7175}$	24
LOHC dehydrogenation unit	$C_{inst} [\text{€}_{2015}] = 3.5 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Hydrogen Flow} [\text{ton/day}]}{1.5} \right)^{0.6}$	20
Metal hydride system	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2021}] = 13744 \cdot (\text{Hydrogen Capacity} [kg])^{0.7509}$	27

⁵⁰ Internal information provided by tanks manufacturer.

Heat pump	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2015}] = 700 \cdot \text{HeatingDemand}[\text{kW}_{th}]$	31
Chiller	$C_{uninst} [\text{€}_{2015}] = 650 \cdot \text{CoolingDemand}[\text{kW}_{th}]$	31

TABLE 3-10: SUMMARY OF YEARLY MAINTENANCE EXPENSES ADOPTED.

Equipment	Yearly maintenance cost [€/yr]
GH2-30 bar storage vessel	1% of CAPEX
GH2-350 bar storage vessel	1% of CAPEX
GH2-350 bar 3-stages reciprocating compressor	4% of CAPEX
LH2 liquefaction unit	4% of CAPEX
LH2 storage vessel	1% of CAPEX
LH2 vaporization unit	1% of CAPEX
LOHC hydrogenation unit	1.5% of CAPEX
LOHC storage vessel	1% of CAPEX
LOHC dehydrogenation unit	3% of CAPEX
Metal hydride system	1.5% of CAPEX
Heat pump	1% of CAPEX
Chiller	1% of CAPEX

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Technical KPIs

In this subsection, the results obtained about the technical KPIs shown in Table 2-1 are presented. As previously stated, the technical KPIs have been evaluated by looking at literature references or datasheets of commercial products.

In the case of the *storage efficiency* for the compressed gaseous hydrogen, it has been evaluated assuming an inlet pressure of 30 bar and several stages function of the compression ratio and the maximum outlet temperature (*Subsection 2.2.2, Section 3.2*). The range of storage efficiency is calculated assuming an isentropic compression with 90% efficiency.

The *volumetric density* and *gravimetric density* have been collected from literature and from some manufacturers' website. In the latter case, the empty-vessel density is adjusted through the *NIST Chemistry WebBook*³³ to also consider the presence of hydrogen at the specified conditions of pressure and temperature. The results obtained are here reported in

Table 4-1.

Parameter	GH2 - 30 bar	GH2 - 350 bar	LH2,	LOHCs	Metal Hydrides	HyCARE [®]
Storage efficiency [kWh/kgH ₂]	ND	1.75 - 2.83	8.00-15.00	7.60-11.20	2.60-6.50	0.5
Gravimetric energy density [kgH ₂ /kg]	0.001-0.003	0.035-0.050	0.056-0.156	0.030-0.050	0.01-0.03	0.012-0.0142
Volumetric energy density [kgH ₂ /m ³]	0.90-3.14	16.72-18.20	13.90-46.10	15.72-50.07	95-105	105
Lifetime [yrs]	20-30	20-30	20-30	20-30	20-30	20-30

TABLE 4-1: TECHNICAL KPIS IN LITERATURE FOR DIFFERENT HYDROGEN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES.

Parameter	GH2 - 30 bar ⁵¹	GH2 - 350 bar ^{52,53}	LH2 ^{54,55}	LOHCs ⁵⁶	Metal Hydrides ⁵⁷	HyCARE ^{58,59,60}
Storage efficiency [kWh/kgH ₂]	ND	1.75 - 2.83	8.00-15.00	7.60-11.20	2.60-6.50	0.5
Gravimetric energy density [kgH ₂ /kg]	0.001-0.003	0.035-0.050	0.056-0.156	0.030-0.050	0.01-0.03	0.012-0.0142
Volumetric energy density [kgH ₂ /m ³]	0.90-3.14	16.72-18.20	13.90-46.10	15.72-50.07	95-105	105
Lifetime [yrs]	20-30	20-30	20-30	20-30	20-30	20-30

⁵¹ The inlet pressure is set to 30 bar, so no compression is needed.

⁵² The inlet pressure is set to 30 bar, the temperature to 25°C and the electric efficiency to 95%. Cooling-related expenses are considered by assuming an intercooling/aftercooling temperature of 25°C and a chiller, for the cold-water production, with EER=2.5. The first and second values represent the results obtained for an isentropic efficiency of 90% and 50%, respectively.

⁵³ Saba Niaz, Taniya Manzoor, Altaf Hussain Pandith, Hydrogen storage: Materials, methods and perspectives, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, Volume 50, 2015, Pages 457-469, ISSN 1364-0321, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.05.011>.

⁵⁴ The storage pressure is set to 2 bar and the temperature to -250°C.

⁵⁵ Abdalla M. Abdalla, Shahzad Hossain, Ozzan B. Nisfindy, Atia T. Azad, Mohamed Dawood, Abul K. Azad, Hydrogen production, storage, transportation, and key challenges with applications: A review, Energy Conversion and Management, Volume 165, 2018, Pages 602-627, ISSN 0196-8904, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.03.088>.

⁵⁶ A. Amos, "Costs of Storing and Transporting Hydrogen" NREL/TP-570-25106, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, November 1998.

⁵⁷ Rahul Krishna, Elby Titus, Maryam Salimian, Olena Okhay, Sivakumar Rajendran, Ananth Rajkumar, J. M. G. Sousa, A. L. C. Ferreira, João Campos Gil and Jose Gracio (2012). Hydrogen Storage for energy application. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5772/51238>

⁵⁸ E. M. Dematteis, F. Cuevas, M. Latroche. Selected alloy characterization. HyCARE. Deliverable 2.2 (2020) <https://zenodo.org/record/3712849#.ZFyUaXZBy5c>

⁵⁹ E. M. Dematteis, F. Cuevas, M. Latroche. Optimized alloy composition. HyCARE. Deliverable 2.1 (2020) <https://zenodo.org/record/3712827#.ZFyWJHZBy5c>

⁶⁰ E. M. Dematteis, N. Berti, F. Cuevas, M. Latroche, M. Baricco. Substitutional effects in TiFe for hydrogen storage: a comprehensive review. Materials Advances (2021). DOI: 10.1039/d1ma00101a

4.2 Economic KPIs

4.2.1 Single size

The boundary conditions of the “Base Scenario” and “Normalized Scenario” can be found in Table 2-3.

Base Scenario

Figure 4-1 shows the CAPEX results obtained for the storage technologies analysed, while Figure 4-2 shows their OPEX, on a yearly base. Each technology bar is divided into four categories: the subcomponents considered in each category are listed below. The *HyCARE* system is separated from the other ones.

- **Production:** Compressor (GH2-350 bar), Liquefier (LH2), Hydrogenation Section (LOHC).
- **Storage:** Vessel (GH-30 bar), Vessel (GH2-350 bar), Vessel (LH2), Vessel (LOHC), All system (Metal Hydride and *HyCARE*).
- **Release:** Vaporiser (LH2), Dehydrogenation Section (LOHC).
- **Engineering:** 30% of CAPEX for each storage technology.

The cost of the land occupied by the single component is included into its CAPEX.

FIGURE 4-1: “BASE SCENARIO” – CAPITAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-2: “BASE SCENARIO” – OPERATIONAL EXPENDITURE.

The results underline how the gaseous form at 30 bar results in the most cost-effective solution due to the system’s simplicity and lower expenses. However, the *HyCARE* system proves to be a competitive solution when compared to other storage technologies at the size of 40 kgH₂. The purchase and installation costs are lower than those of liquid hydrogen and LOHCs, and slightly higher than gaseous hydrogen at 350 bar and MH solutions due to the PCM cost. On the other side, the *HyCARE* system shows an OPEX lower than those related to LH₂, LOHCs, GH₂-350 bar and MH systems thanks to the efficient heat exchange system, resulting higher only to the GH₂-30 technology. A good agreement is also found with the metal hydride solution: the presence of the heat management system (PCM) slightly increases the capital expenditure, while it slightly decreases the operational ones due to the thermal “savings” made by the PCM itself. The total cost of ownership is showed in Figure 4-3. The *HyCARE* system results are competitive and comparable with other metal hydrides and gaseous compressed at 350 bar solutions for 40 kg H₂ storage.

FIGURE 4-3: “BASE SCENARIO” – TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP.

From Figure 4-4 to 4-9 are reported the CAPEX breakdown of all storage technologies analyzed.

FIGURE 4-4: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE GH2-30 SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-5: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE GH2-350 SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-6: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE LH2 SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-7: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE LOHC SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-8: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE MH SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-9: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE HYCARE SYSTEM.

Table 4-2 and Figure 4-10 shows in a compact way all detailed CAPEX comparison for each storage technology analyzed.

TABLE 4-2: CAPEX BREAKDOWN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES COMPARISON.

Storage Techs	Vessels	Compressors	Chiller&HPs	Land	Pellets	Liquefier	Vaporizer	Hydrogenation unit	Dehydrogenation unit	Initial DBT	PCM	Solar thermal	Engineering	Total
GH2-30	50,38%	0,00%	0,00%	34,51%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	15,11%	100,00%
GH2-350	63,16%	8,69%	0,20%	6,34%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	21,61%	100,00%
LH2	3,36%	0,00%	0,00%	16,39%	0,00%	60,73%	0,22%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	19,29%	100,00%
LOHC	0,52%	0,00%	2,32%	6,12%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	27,40%	41,75%	0,22%	0,00%	0,00%	21,66%	100,00%
MH-TiFe	29,53%	0,00%	0,69%	3,15%	44,29%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	22,35%	100,00%
HyCARE	24,03%	0,00%	0,00%	3,37%	35,69%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	12,07%	2,53%	22,30%	100,00%

FIGURE 4-10: CAPEX BREAKDOWN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES COMPARISON.

From a comparison, it is possible to underline as for *HyCARE* storage technology, the land cost is less than 4% of the overall CAPEX, so the impact of land is very low. The most impacting component is represented by pellets (35.69%), followed by storage vessels (24.03%). Also, PCM (12.07%) must be taken into consideration. Table 4-2 also provides important insights into the various technologies, showing how each technology has a different cost driver. In fact, both gaseous storage technologies have the most expensive component in the vessel, while LH2 have the liquefaction unit and LOHC in the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation units. Finally, MH and *HyCARE* are heavily dependent on the cost of pellets.

Figure 4-12 reports the breakdown of *HyCARE* operative expenditures. 55% of the whole cost is related to the vessel and alloy maintenance, and another 44% is related to substitution over lifetime. The PCM module replacement is not included in the breakdown because it has an extremely high lifetime (>30 years selected for the TEA). Last but not least, the electricity, heating and cooling cost weighs less than 1% of OPEX.

FIGURE 4-11: OPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE HYCARE SYSTEM.

Figures 4-12 and 4-13 show the LCoS and the actualized LCoS, respectively.

FIGURE 4-12: “BASE SCENARIO” – LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

FIGURE 4-13: “BASE SCENARIO” – ACTUALISED LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

For the base “Base Scenario” the best storage solution, for a 40-kg system size, is the gaseous compressed hydrogen at 30 bar, both in the non-actualised example that in the actualised one due to the design simplicity (no compressor or other additional device, a part storage vessel is needed). The *HyCARE* system with an actualized LCoS equal to 82.13 €/kg proves to be competitive comparable with the GH2-350 bar and commercial metal hydride solutions, and better than LH2 and LOHC technologies.

Normalised Scenario

Figure 4- shows the CAPEX results obtained for the storage technologies analysed, while Figure 4- shows their OPEX, on a yearly base. Also in this case, each technology bar is divided into four categories, which are the same adopted for the “Base Scenario” analysis. By comparing

Figure 4-14 and Figure 4-15 with Figure 4-16 and 17, it can be noticed that:

- An increase in the input maximum hydrogen flow (production peak) reflects higher CAPEX for components whose capital cost scales with the production rate (i.e., liquefier, compressor, hydrogenation unit).
- The more intense working regime cause the operational expenditure to be higher in the “Normalised Scenario” (N.S.) than in the “Base Scenario” (B.S.). This is caused by the fact that in the B.S. the storage system is filled and then completely emptied. Hence, during the emptying phase the production units (e.g., liquefier, compressor etc.) do not work, and the same happens for the release units during the filling phase. On the contrary, in the N.S. the

filling and emptying phase occur simultaneously; thus, all units work during all the annual operative hours.

FIGURE 4-14: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – CAPITAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-15: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – OPERATIONAL EXPENDITURE.

Also in this case, the *HyCARE* solution has CAPEX and OPEX comparable with the gaseous technology at 350bar and with the metal hydride one. OPEX turns out to be very advantageous and the gap of *HyCARE* over MH becomes larger due to the intensive use of the storage system in this case study.

The total cost of ownership is shown in Figure 4-. As can be seen, the *HyCARE* system results are competitive with other metal hydrides, and the solid-state storage systems are much cheaper than the GH2-350 bar solution. The peculiarity in the normalized case study is given by the fact that the intense

exploitation of the storage system highlights a greater impact of OPEX. Consequently, *HyCARE* OPEX is very low, lower than the MH solution, which translates into an extremely advantageous TCO, slightly better than the MHs. Also, in the “Normalised Scenario” the GH2-30 bar solution proves to be the most cost-effective strategy to store 40 kgH₂.

FIGURE 4-16: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP.

As for the base scenario, Figures 4-17 to 4-22 show the breakdown of the CAPEX of the various storage technologies.

FIGURE 4-17: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE GH2-30 SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-18: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE GH2-350 SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-19: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE LH2 SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-20: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE LOHC SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-21: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE MH SYSTEM.

FIGURE 4-22: CAPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE HyCARE SYSTEM.

Table 4-3 and Figure 4-23 shows in a compact way all detailed CAPEX comparison for each storage technology analyzed.

TABLE 4-3: CAPEX BREAKDOWN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES COMPARISON.

Storage Techs	Vessels	Compressors	Chiller&HPs	Land	Pellets	Liquefier	Vaporizer	Hydrogenation unit	Dehydrogenation unit	Initial DBT	PCM	Solar thermal	Engineering	Total
GH2-30	50,38%	0,00%	0,00%	34,51%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	15,11%	100,00%
GH2-350	37,15%	34,03%	2,71%	3,96%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	22,16%	100,00%
LH2	0,53%	0,00%	0,00%	5,03%	0,00%	72,45%	0,08%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	21,92%	100,00%
LOHC	0,12%	0,00%	7,08%	5,79%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40,45%	24,77%	0,05%	0,00%	0,00%	21,74%	100,00%
MH-TiFe	28,52%	0,00%	3,28%	3,04%	42,78%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	22,38%	100,00%
HyCARE	24,03%	0,00%	0,00%	3,37%	35,69%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	12,07%	2,53%	22,30%	100,00%

FIGURE 4-23: CAPEX BREAKDOWN STORAGE TECHNOLOGIES COMPARISON.

From a comparison, as in the base scenario, it is possible to underline as for *HyCARE* storage technology the land cost is less than 4% of the overall CAPEX, so the impact of land is low. The most impacting component is represented by pellets (>35%), followed by storage vessels (>24%).

Table 4-3 provides important insights into the various technologies, showing how each technology has a different cost driver. In fact, both gaseous storage technologies have the most expensive component in the vessel and compressor for 350 bar only, while LH2 have the liquefaction unit and LOHC in the hydrogenation and dehydrogenation units. Finally, MH and *HyCARE* are heavily dependent on the cost of pellets. Figure 4- shows the breakdown of *HyCARE* operative expenditures.

FIGURE 4-24: OPEX BREAKDOWN FOR THE HYCARE SYSTEM.

The main cost driver of *HyCARE* OPEX is due to vessel, alloy, and BoP maintenance cost (55%).

Figure 4-25 and 4-26 show the non-actualised and actualised levelized cost of storage breakdown for all the analyzed technologies.

FIGURE 4-25: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

FIGURE 4-26: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – ACTUALISED LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

Figure 4-25 shows how, in terms of non-actualised LCoS, the HyCARE system appears to be very competitive, resulting in being the best solution behind only the GH2-30, thanks to the high OPEX advantage. This is the result of a more intense working regime, in which the total hydrogen produced is greater than the one released in the “Base Scenario”. Comparing **Error! Reference source not found.** with 4-10 the levelized cost of storage decrease for all technologies.

Figure 4-26 instead considers the actualized rates, allowing the MH to surpass *HyCARE* technology (5.01 €/kg vs 5.39 €/kg), while *HyCARE* remains a competitive technology better than GH2-350, LH2 and LOHC.

In order to perform a complete comparison of the various technologies it is important to compare the overall dimensions of the various technologies for a 40 kg-H₂ storage (Table 4-4).

TABLE 4-4: COMPARISON BETWEEN 40KG STORAGE TECHNOLOGY FOOTPRINT.

Storage Technology	Footprint / m ²
GH2-30	342.25
GH2-350	396.13
LH2	5331.11
LOHC	2379.95
MH-TiFe	171.43
HyCARE	204.60

*Storage tanks for GH2-30 and GH2-350 technologies have been considered in vertical position.

It should be noted that the footprint of the *HyCARE* storage system for 40 kg of hydrogen is respectively equal to 59.7% and 51.6% compared to that of GH2-30 and GH2-350. Therefore, where there is a constraint in terms of space available for accumulation, the *HyCARE* and “common” MH storage would certainly be the preferred solution. Furthermore, if the tanks are placed in a horizontal position, the overall dimensions of the GH2-30 and GH2-350 would increase, as would the gap with respect to the *HyCARE* and MHs.

4.2.2 Single-size sensitivity analysis

Within the sensitivity analysis, the influence of three main parameters on the systems’ TCO has been explored. These parameters are:

- The land cost [€/m²].
- The external safety distance [m].
- The cost of electricity [€/MWh].

In the external safety distance sensitivity analysis, the imposed distance is the same for all the system (i.e., it is not considered the low dangerousness of LOHCs, metal hydrides and *HyCARE* on the contrary of what has been presented before). In the following paragraphs, the acronyms “B.S.” and “N.S.” refer to the “Base Scenario” and “Normalised Scenario”, respectively.

Base Scenario

In Figure 4-27, it is reported the influence of the land cost on the capital expenditure and total cost of ownership of the storage systems, varying the land cost from 0 to 400 €/m². It can be seen how the cost of land highly influences the CAPEX and, therefore, the TCO. OPEX costs are not reported because land does not impact OPEX.

The CAPEX of technologies like metal hydrides and *HyCARE*, which have a low footprint (as per Table 4-4), scale slightly with the cost of the land. For a 40 kgH₂ system, *HyCARE* CAPEX and TCO increase slightly with a land cost increase, due to the small impact of land in solid-state storage technologies. The biggest impact of land cost is experienced by technologies such as LH2 and LOHC having a very impactful footprint.

FIGURE 4-27: “BASE SCENARIO” - LAND COST SENSITIVITY STUDY.

Figure 4-28 shows the influence of the external safety distance on the CAPEX and TCO of the system, varying the external safety distance from 0 to 50m. The external distance highly influences technologies like liquid, and liquid organic technologies, but it influences less also *HyCARE* and metal hydride systems. Moreover, it must be noticed that in this analysis the external safety distances are equal for all systems, even if LOHCs, metal hydrides and *HyCARE* are low-hazard technologies. Therefore, this comparison overestimates the CAPEX and TCO of the above mentioned technologies. In any case, the increase in the safety distance does not have a big impact, because the cost of the land has a limited impact on the CAPEX of the various storage technologies (34% for CH₂-30, less than 20% for all other technologies).

FIGURE 4-28: “BASE SCENARIO” - EXTERNAL SAFETY DISTANCE SENSITIVITY STUDY.

Finally, Figure 4-29 shows the impact of the electricity cost on the operative expenditure and the total cost of ownership, varying the electricity cost from 30 to 250 €/MWh. There is no impact on CAPEX. For various storage technologies, the influence of the change in electricity cost has a different impact. Technologies such as GH2-30 and *HyCARE* have a constant (no energy consumption for GH2-30) or almost constant trend (for *HyCARE*) because the increase in the cost of electricity is irrelevant. Technologies such as GH2-350 and MH have a slight increase due to the cost of compressors, heating, and cooling systems. The impact is even greater in liquid storage technologies, as they are particularly energy intensive (for liquefaction).

FIGURE 4-29: “BASE SCENARIO” - COST OF ELECTRICITY SENSITIVITY STUDY.

Normalised Scenario

In Figure 4-30 it is reported the influence of the land cost on the capital expenditure and total cost of ownership of the storage systems investigated by means of the same land cost range. The CAPEX and TCO trends reflect what is reported in the base scenario, with some technologies, such as MH, *HyCARE* and GH2-350 having little impact from this cost driver. The impact is rather significant for liquid storage technologies, above all LH2. The *HyCARE* solution results slightly expensive than commercial metal hydrides for all the analyzed land costs.

FIGURE 4-30: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” - LAND COST SENSITIVITY STUDY.

Figure 4-31 shows the influence of the external safety distance on the CAPEX and TCO of the system. The trends plotted are like the ones obtained for the “Base Scenario” with MH and *HyCARE* less affected by the variation of this parameter than liquid storage technologies.

FIGURE 4-31: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – EXTERNAL SAFETY DISTANCE SENSITIVITY STUDY.

Finally, Figure 4-32 shows the impact of the electricity cost on the operative expenditure and the total cost of ownership. The increase in the electricity price still has little influence on the economic KPIs of the systems; however, it can be noticed that in the “Normalised Scenario” this influence is greater than in the “Base Scenario”, because of the more intense working regime and, thus, the higher utilities requirement. An OPEX comparison between solid phase storage technologies shows how the *HyCARE* system, thanks to the integrated heat exchange system, has a lower energy consumption and, therefore, a lower cost associated with electricity than metal hydrides. The *HyCARE* OPEX has an almost constant trend when the cost of electricity varies.

FIGURE 4-32: “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – COST OF ELECTRICITY SENSITIVITY STUDY.

4.2.3 Multiple size

The multiple-size analysis aims to evaluate how the different storage technologies behave when the storage capacity is scaled-up or scaled down. Two different ranges of capacity are here analyzed for both the “Base Scenario” and “Normalised Scenario”:

- A small to medium size range: from 1 to 250 kg of stored hydrogen.
- A medium to large size range: from 250 to 2500 kg of stored hydrogen.

Base Scenario

Error! Reference source not found., 4-34, 4-35 and 4-36 show the specific capital expenditure (capex), operational expenditure (opex), the total cost of ownership (tco) and levelized cost of storage (LCoS) for the analyzed technologies, for storage capacities between 1 and 250 kg of hydrogen. The economic assumptions used to obtain these results are those in Table 3-1. For the scaling up of the metal hydrides, the Eq. 3-16 of the learning curve has been used and calculated using *OriginLab* software. The 40 kg MH hydrogen storage developed in *HyCARE* project is represented by a black dot.

FIGURE 4-33: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - “BASE SCENARIO” – SPECIFIC CAPITAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-34: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - “BASE SCENARIO” – SPECIFIC OPERATIONAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-35: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - “BASE SCENARIO” – SPECIFIC TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP.

FIGURE 4-36: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - “BASE SCENARIO” – LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

For the whole range of small to medium capacities analyzed, the GH2-30 bar system results the most competitive in terms of capex, opex, tco and LCoS, while the *HyCARE* system shows a scaling behavior better than GH2-350 bar in terms of capex, opex and tco but a tco and LCoS worse than commercial metal hydrides (from around 75 kgH₂ on). With the increase in size, the LCoS of *HyCARE* improves slightly, going from 36.2 €/kg for 25 kg storage to 25.8 €/kg for 250 kg storage. With the storage size increase, LH2 and LOHC liquid storage technologies begin to be comparable, even if more expensive than other storage technologies, testifying to the fact that these technologies are suitable for large storage sizes.

Error! Reference source not found. 4-38, 4-39 and 4-40 show the capex, opex, tco and LCoS for medium to large storages up to 2500 kg of hydrogen.

FIGURE 4-37: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - “BASE SCENARIO” – SPECIFIC CAPITAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-38: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - "BASE SCENARIO" – SPECIFIC OPERATIONAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-39: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - "BASE SCENARIO" – SPECIFIC TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP.

FIGURE 4-40: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - “BASE SCENARIO” – LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

Comparing the tco in Figure 4-39, the best technology is always gaseous storage at 30 bar, however the advantage compared to other technologies is slimmer. *HyCARE* appears to lose competitiveness compared to metal hydrides due to higher CAPEX and substantially similar OPEX than MH solution. Technologies such as LOHC become competitive and better than *HyCARE* for storage bigger than 875 kg. While the LH2 technology for storage of 2500 kg approaches the MH. Storage at 350 bar, on the other hand, is the worst technology due to the high cost of the tanks. With the increase in size, the LCoS of *HyCARE* system decreases exponentially until it reaches 21.2 €/kg for a storage of 2500 kg.

Normalised Scenario

Error! Reference source not found., 4-42, 4-43 and 4-44 show the specific capital expenditure (capex), operational expenditure (opex), total cost of ownership (tco) and levelized cost of storage (LCoS) for the analyzed technologies, for storage capacities between 1 and 250 kg of hydrogen. Also in this case, the 40 kg MH hydrogen storage developed in *HyCARE* project is represented by a black dot.

FIGURE 4-41: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - "NORMALISED SCENARIO" – SPECIFIC CAPITAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-42: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - "NORMALISED SCENARIO" – SPECIFIC OPERATIONAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-43: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – SPECIFIC TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP.

FIGURE 4-44: MULTIPLE SIZE (1-250KG) - “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

The normalized scenario, with more intensive use of the storage system, rewards the *HyCARE* system, which, thanks to the low OPEX, has a TCO that is always better than MH, GH2-350, LH2 and LOHC for the whole range of small-medium storage size (up to 250 kg). The cheapest and most expensive technologies are always, respectively, as in the base scenario, GH2-30 and LH2. The intensive operation and the large quantity of H₂ stored yearly in the normalized scenario, drastically minimize the LCoS for *HyCARE* system (from 36.2 €/kg of B.S. to 2.30 €/kg of N.S.) for 25 kg H₂ storage and (from 25.2 €/kg of B.S. to 1.64 €/kg of N.S.) for 250 kg H₂ storage.

The Figures 4-45, 4-46, 4-47 and 4-48 show the multidimensional analysis for medium and large storage systems (250-2500 kg).

FIGURE 4-45: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - "NORMALISED SCENARIO" – SPECIFIC CAPITAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-46: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - "NORMALISED SCENARIO" – SPECIFIC OPERATIONAL EXPENDITURE.

FIGURE 4-47: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – SPECIFIC TOTAL COST OF OWNERSHIP.

FIGURE 4-48: MULTIPLE SIZE (250-2500KG) - “NORMALISED SCENARIO” – LEVELISED COST OF STORAGE.

Despite the large storage dimensions, a careful examination of the TCO and LCoS (Figure 4-47 and 4-48) show how, due to high energy consumption, the LH2 and LOHC technologies are not competitive or even comparable, despite what happened in the base scenario. The winning technology always turns out to be the GH2-30. On the other side, *HyCARE* and metal hydrides have an almost equal to throughout the 250-2500 kg range, resulting better compared to liquid and high-pressure gaseous storages. The LCoS is further reduced to 1.35 €/kg for 2500 kg H2 storage.

5. Conclusions

Deliverable D8.2 provided a technical-economic analysis of liquid, gaseous and solid storage technologies for the storage of 40 kg H₂.

Chapter 1 showed an overview of the various technologies analyzed, defining the type of analysis performed, single-size and multi-dimensional, the type of scenarios identified, base and normalized, and defining the technical and economic KPIs to be calculated, thus describing the methodology used for the study. For each of the scenarios identified, the control volumes and boundary conditions were defined, as well as the operating parameters.

After that, Chapter 2 analyzed the various storage technologies in detail, identifying the process flow diagram and the main cost items for each one.

The third chapter explained in detail the equations of the cost items of each piece of equipment obtained by literature and by use of dedicated calculation software, such as *Matlab* and *Originlab*, identifying in tabular form all the assumptions made in terms of OPEX, other useful parameters for analysis and the equations used to calculate CAPEX.

Chapter 4 was dedicated to the discussion of the results. After comparing the technical KPIs, which highlighted how solid storage technologies and the *HyCARE* system are characterized by an extremely high volumetric density and a lifetime comparable to other storage technologies, the chapter discussed the economic KPIs. Firstly, the single-size analysis for the storage of 40 kg of H₂ has shown how:

For the *Base Scenario*:

- *HyCARE* technology appears to be particularly competitive, with a TCO slightly higher than MH, due to the high cost of PCM, but much better than other GH₂-350, LH₂ and LOHC technologies.
- The main cost driver for *HyCARE* CAPEX is represented by the cost of vessels and pellets (60%). The cost of the land has a negligible impact of 3.3% while the PCM weighs for more than 12%.
- The OPEX costs of the *HyCARE* system are mainly linked to vessel, alloy & BoP maintenance, and their replacement (together count for 94% of the OPEX). Electricity, heating, and cooling have a marginal weight (<1%).
- With actualized LCoS of 82.13 €/kg, *HyCARE* is more expensive than the MHs solution (69.34 €/kg) and the GH₂-350 (78.31 €/kg).

For the *Normalised Scenario*:

- The large use of the storage system results in higher energy, heating and cooling consumption, leveraging storage systems such as *HyCARE*, which have very advantageous OPEX. In fact, *HyCARE* ranks right behind GH₂-30, better than MH and GH₂-350, LH₂ and LOHC.
- *HyCARE* actualized LCoS is slightly higher than MH (5.39 €/kg vs 5.01 €/kg) but clearly lower than GH₂-350 (9.75 €/kg) and other liquid storage technologies.

- The footprint of *HyCARE* and metal hydrides is significantly smaller than other storage technologies (59% of GH2-30 footprint, 51% compared to GH2-350, 8.6% of LOHC footprint and 3.8% compared to LH2).

Furthermore, to evaluate the impact of some key parameters on the competitiveness of various storage technologies examined, a sensitivity analysis was performed on the cost of the land, on the safety distances and on the cost of the electricity for both investigated scenarios. In this regard, the cost of the land was varied from 0 to 400 €/m², the safety distances were varied between 0 and 50 m, the electricity cost was varied between 30 and 250 €/MWh.

For the *Base Scenario*:

- Solid storage technologies such as *HyCARE*, due to the high volumetric density that results in a small footprint, are little affected by the variation in the cost of the land.
- For the same reason mentioned above, the variation of safety distances does not greatly impact solid storage technologies, while LOHC is the most affected technology.
- The limited energy consumption of *HyCARE* makes the system less influenced by the variation in the cost of electricity, with an almost constant trend. The worst technology is LH2 due to the very energy-intensive liquefaction process.

For the *Normalised Scenario*:

- The variation in the cost of land has a negligible impact on solid storage technologies but results in a strong impact on technologies like LH2 with a large footprint.
- The impact of the variation of the safety distances for *HyCARE* is not relevant, due to the small size of the storage.
- The *HyCARE* system, thanks to the integrated heat exchange system, has a lower energy consumption and, therefore, a lower cost associated with electricity than metal hydrides, liquid, and high-pressure storage technologies.

Furthermore, the report analyzed the scalability of various small to medium (1-250 kg H₂) and medium to large (250-2500 kg H₂) storage technologies, in order to identify which technology is most suitable for a specific storage size. In this regard, the economic KPIs capex, opex, tco and LCoS were assessed for both scenarios. For the scalability of the *HyCARE* system, the learning curve approach was used, based on the CAPEX inputs received by the partners, and processing these data on *Originlab* to determine the learning curve scalability function (see Eq. 3.16).

For the *Base Scenario*:

- For small to medium size storage, *HyCARE* is worse than metal hydrides for storage above 75 kg H₂. As the storage size increased, the *HyCARE* system's LCoS decreased from 36.2 €/kg to 25.8 €/kg for 250 kg-H₂ storage.
- For medium to large storage, due to the low utilization of the storage system, *HyCARE* seems to lose competitiveness compared to MHs, with an ever higher specific TCO. LOHC also appears to have a lower TCO than *HyCARE* for storages exceeding 875 kg H₂ and LH2 for storages higher than 2500 kg H₂.

- LCoS of *HyCARE* decreases from 25.8 €/kg for 250 kg H₂ to 21.2 €/kg for 2500 kg H₂.

For the *Normalised Scenario*:

- For small to medium size storage, being an energy intensive scenario, *HyCARE* takes advantage of its integrated heat exchange characteristics, generating a better tco than GH₂-350, MH, LOCH and LH₂ for all range sizes.
- The greater annual quantity of H₂ stored drastically lowers the LCoS which passes for from 36.2 €/kg of B.S. to 2.30 €/kg of N.S. for 25 kg H₂ storage, and from 25.2 €/kg of B.S. to 1.64 €/kg of N.S. for 250 kg H₂ storage.
- For medium to large storage, MH and *HyCARE* show similar TCO across the entire size range, with an almost linear trend; unlike the base scenario, the LH₂ and LCOH technologies fail to reach the competitiveness of solid storage systems.
- LCoS of *HyCARE* decreases from 1.64 €/kg to 1.35 €/kg passing from 250 kg to 2500 kg-H₂.

Finally, a series of future activities have been identified with the aim of largely improve the accuracy and impact of this study. The following points should be investigated more:

- Improve the learning cost curve

The upscaling of novel technologies has a relevant lack of economic data, so evaluating a big-scale system is challenging. A possible approach is the application of a learning cost curve, a power-law relation which introduces the discount rate of a system every double of size or production capacity. In this sense, additional activity should focus on gathering economic data for metal hydride solutions with a dedicated survey on active players, aiming at defining a more reliable upscaling cost.

- Safety distance and land occupation

Safety distance is relevant to land occupation for several H₂ storage technologies. While the compressed gas system has regulations or codes to respect, metal hydride solutions can approach lower safety distances due to lower pressure and correlated hazards. A better definition of safety distance can improve the metal hydride system's economics (lowering civil and ancillary works and costs). Conversely, an effective techno-economics assessment must include real limitations regarding the area and volume of the H₂ storage system, which can also exclude several technologies. Indeed as reported in Table 4-4, metal hydride solution and *HyCARE* show lower land occupation than other solutions, which make such technology affordable and suitable for application where available space is strongly limited.

Finally, a comment about comparing pure metal hydride solution and the *HyCARE* system: formally, this TEA shows a slight economic advantage for using metal hydride solution instead of the *HyCARE* system. However, the user cases included in this work do not consider all operative aspects that an H₂ storage system must respond to and are required to be carefully quantified in terms of operative cost. Among them, standby time and operative cost for the absorption/desorption step can strongly impact the cost for the H₂ storage, particularly when no continuous operation (notable standby time) or high frequency of discharge/charge of the system is considered. In these conditions, the *HyCARE*

system has a clear advantage in terms of availability, introducing large thermal inertia on the system (PCM) with an high heat exchange capability, guaranteeing temperature stability even for long standby periods, and heat source and sink for rapid desorption or absorption processes (so reducing auxiliars).